

UK National Strategy for Global Environmental Research

*Inter-Agency Committee on
Global Environmental Change:
Report of Expert Panel*

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Preface

A hundred years ago the Earth was, relatively speaking, sparsely populated by human beings. But our numbers are doubling roughly every 30 years, and this explosion of our population is now driving changes in our physical and biological environment that are potentially damaging and in some cases irreversible. Until we understand them, there can be little confidence either in our ability to recognise harmful changes sufficiently early, or in our attempts to take steps to mitigate them.

Global environmental change is no respecter of national frontiers. No one country, even if it wished to do so, could solve the problems by itself. Both for this reason and because of the sheer size of the task, the problems have to be tackled by international collaborative research programmes and by national programmes that are complementary to each other. It goes without saying that within single countries, every effort must be made to have programmes that are as far as possible mutually supportive, and make sense in a broader international context.

Within the UK work relevant to Global Environmental Research (GER) is carried out or supported by a number of different agencies. They meet regularly at a senior level on the Inter-Agency Committee for Global Environmental Change (IACGEC)* under the auspices of the Office of Science and Technology. That committee set the broad policy objectives for the work of two successive expert groups under the chairmanship of Professor Brian Hoskins. They first reviewed the work that was already in hand in the UK, looking for overlaps, complementarities and possible new synergies. They then set about the job of framing a national programme that on the one hand satisfied the diverse needs of the component agencies and on the other was set in the context of the international efforts on GER. This report is the outcome of their work and, furthermore, takes into account comments arising from a period of public consultation.

There are of course many local environmental problems that are in one sense global because they are widespread, but in another are not, insofar as they can be tackled with local methods to give local relief; traffic congestion, traffic generated health problems, polluted drinking water are just a few examples. Matters such as these fall outside the scope of this report even though they are major concerns for some of its sponsoring bodies, not because they are unimportant but because they are different in kind.

Although I hope that this report will be of interest and value to the scientific community, I hope too that it will be useful to those both in industry and in government concerned with setting policy by giving them an insight both into the problems that we face and into the methods that are being used to tackle them.

Finally, I wish to place on record my gratitude to Brian Hoskins and his two working groups. I believe that they have done an outstanding job and one that will give added coherence to the UK effort in Global Environmental Research, thus allowing all concerned to make use of the resources that are available in the most cost effective way, and to complement the work carried out by colleagues in other countries.

* See over for list of member agencies

Sir Robert May FRS
Chief Scientific Adviser
Office of Science and Technology

Acknowledgement

In its early deliberations Expert Panel II drew upon the submissions from many senior researchers (Annex 3) who responded to a consultation exercise. These were supplemented by further comments on a pre-final draft during and after a consultation conference held in March 1996 at the Royal Geographical Society. Such material was of considerable value and the Expert Panel and IACGEC wish to express their gratitude for the time and effort taken to attend the conference and submit written comments.

Inter-Agency Committee on Global Environmental Change (IACGEC)

Chairman: Sir Ronald Oxburgh KBE, FRS (Rector, Imperial College, London)

Biotechnology and Biological Sciences Research Council (BBSRC)

British National Space Centre (BNSC)

Department of the Environment (DoE) - represents all Government Departments

Economic and Social Research Council (ESRC)

Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council (EPSRC)

Medical Research Council (MRC)

Meteorological Office

Natural Environment Research Council (NERC)

Office of Science and Technology - Observer

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Executive Summary

1. Rationale and scope

1.1 Human actions are altering global-scale environmental properties and processes in ways that have many unknown implications. With projected increases in human population, per capita consumption and global economic trade, the impacts of these actions will grow. Implementing policies for sustainable development requires a better understanding of the dynamic relationships between socio-economic activities and natural systems.

1.2 Global environmental research (GER) addresses these issues, by investigating the processes of the integrated Earth system. Its overall goals are to: identify, explain and predict anthropogenic changes in the global environment, in the context of natural variability; assess the potential regional and local impacts of those changes on natural and human systems, including their implications for policy and law; and assist in developing appropriate responses.

1.3 The concept of GER is still evolving and maturing. GER is both multi- and interdisciplinary, involving many systems operating over a wide range of spatial and temporal scales. Knowledge of the interplay between these different systems, across these scales, is critical to the understanding of global environmental change.

1.4 The dynamic properties of interacting, global-scale systems preclude total predictability. Hence, recognising and addressing uncertainty is a key theme for GER. New observational, analytical and theoretical tools provide opportunities not only for major advances in scientific understanding, but also for improved risk assessments, scenario development and policy formulation.

1.5 UK strengths in GER provide an information advantage in a changing world, underpinning many aspects of economic activity and policy development at the national, regional and global level. More than 20 generic priorities (from eight Panels) of the 1995 Technology Foresight exercise are closely relevant to GER (Table 1). Many economic sectors benefit from GER results, as illustrated in Table 2.

1.6 Much of the current GER effort has been directly stimulated by interest in global environmental change. However, a wide range of other studies that have primarily been developed for other reasons also contribute to GER. These boundary problems make it difficult for funding agencies to estimate their individual support for GER on a consistent basis. Nevertheless, the current UK effort on GER-relevant work is estimated at £180m p.a. and is similar in scale to that of estimates from other developed countries. Investment should remain at least at this level.

1.7 European and international GER programmes add considerable value to the UK research effort. Strong participation in such programmes accelerates research progress, facilitates access to international funding and other resources, provides opportunities for scientific leadership and enhances national credibility and influence in international negotiations.

1.8 The UK is now party to several hundred international environmental obligations and arrangements. In addition, many other international agreements have environmental implications. The effective implementation of such agreements requires commitments by both developed and developing countries, with associated needs for building GER-related research capacity in the latter.

2. Research directions and priorities

2.1 The pervasive and multidisciplinary nature of GER defies linear analysis or simple compartmentalisation. The conceptual approach proposed by the Panel is shown in the GER triad (Figure 2). It comprises three perspectives (the human, physico-chemical and biological systems), with research at three levels (underpinning, interactive and systemic research) according to the strength of linkages between components. As GER matures and evolves, the need for new connections between different scientific fields becomes increasingly important.

2.2 Underpinning GER provides the fundamental knowledge and technological capabilities. Major uncertainties and new scientific issues continue to emerge in this underpinning category, and satisfactory attention to these issues is the foundation for evolving and maturing work in the interactive and systemic categories. Priority topics for underpinning GER are identified in section 2.2.

2.3 Interactive GER involves linkages between at least two of the three main scientific perspectives, investigating how one system affects another. Research on interactive issues considered to be of particular importance are covered in section 2.3.

2.4 Systemic GER provides the overall framework, building on underpinning and interactive GER to address the 'grand challenges' of Earth system science. Four main integrative themes are identified; integrated climate studies, biogeochemical cycles, land use and water resources, and ozone and UV-B.

2.5 Building upon and complementing the generic GER priorities outlined in sections 2.2 to 2.4, six scientific growth points are highlighted, on the basis that their inter-agency stimulation would give highly cost-effective benefits (section 2.5).

2.6 Recognising that the UK cannot cover all aspects of science in depth, the issues highlighted seek to build upon areas of excellence and are largely consistent with priorities identified in agency portfolios.

3. Enabling technologies and infrastructure

3.1 Research aircraft and ships are essential for *in situ* measurements to investigate atmospheric and oceanic processes, and to calibrate space measurements. The availability of Earth observation data from satellites offers many exciting research opportunities, but in order to optimise the benefits of these satellites it is essential there be an increasing emphasis on the use of observations in analysis and modelling.

3.2 The UK GER effort currently benefits from a wide range of land-based facilities for monitoring and experimental work, with relatively well-developed environmental capabilities in public sector laboratories and universities. Future arrangements for their support should recognise these roles.

3.3 The maintenance of current national observational facilities would provide a basic UK input to the three proposed Global Observing Systems (for Climate, Ocean and Terrestrial Systems).

3.4 Progress in modelling (and predicting) global environmental change requires continued access to powerful supercomputers, together with facilities for the processing, storage and interactive interpretation of high-volume data.

3.5 In order to make the widest and most effective national use of data resources, it is desirable that data charges for scientific research of a non-commercial nature should be set as low as possible.

4. Communication and coordination

4.1 Those involved in GER need to establish constructive dialogue with the users and beneficiaries of their work and to give greater attention to the wider issues of public awareness and perception, with particular care taken to address uncertainty in a societal context.

4.2 Education and training are essential at all levels to ensure both the future cadre of scientists of the quality required by GER and also a proper basis for informed public debate. The UK should play a leading international role in knowledge and technology transfer.

4.3 The increasing complexity of the science agenda and the inter-dependence of funding agencies' interests in GER (Figure 3) highlight the increasing requirements for effective coordination and collaboration. The current structure of the Inter-Agency Committee on Global Environmental Change (IACGEC) is primarily directed at overall policy issues. It would seem advantageous to also have a unified forum for the scientific development of GER.

1. What is GER and why is it needed?

1.1 Defining the problem

1.1.1 Rationale

It is clear that human beings are having a profound effect on the environment in which they live. In some cases the effects are potentially damaging to human life and may be irreversible. The overall aim of Global Environmental Research is to understand the global interplay between natural processes and human activity. Global environmental research (GER) embodies a distinct shift in the way that we acquire and use knowledge about human society and the natural world. It is only within the past decade that GER has acquired its distinct identity. The questions that it addresses are not all new; however, the need to answer these questions has become more urgent, and the means to do so are now becoming available, using novel technological and theoretical tools.

It now seems likely that the level of human activity that can be supported by this finite planet will be set by critical changes in atmospheric composition, altering the global heat budget and freshwater availability, rather than by absolute shortages of energy or mineral resources.

Many aspects of the Earth's climate and elemental cycles have been successfully investigated, and, in a simplified way, their behaviour can now be modelled. Whilst further global-scale environmental changes seem inevitable, affecting both the developed and the developing world, actions are being initiated to reduce or adapt to their damaging effects. The concept of sustainable development is now widely accepted, and international frameworks have been set up for the scientific assessment of global change problems and policy formulation.

We also now know that interacting systems (both natural and societal) often behave in novel ways when perturbed. Whilst adaptive responses may suffice for slow, progressive changes, it is much harder to prepare for sudden, unexpected events. Under such circumstances, full predictability of future environmental behaviour is unachievable. Instead, we must aim to determine the limits of predictability - to minimise the risk of unpleasant

surprises, whilst learning how to develop policy responses based on scenarios, rather than certainties.

The overall goal of GER is therefore to acquire the knowledge on this interplay between natural processes and human activities, in ways that will have long term benefit for human well-being (see Box 1 for a more comprehensive definition). The need for such understanding necessitates the funding of sustained national GER programmes that complement each other. Global environmental change brings opportunities as well as risks, and those nations that are best-informed will be best placed to derive benefit from those changes. Gaps in national expertise can be particularly critical for components of GER that are regionally specific or culturally dependent. For some technological aspects, research results can be more readily transferable: there may therefore be no need for a country such as the UK to tackle issues being effectively addressed elsewhere. However, the scale of many problems demands a worldwide effort. All GER work is dependent on the activities of a wider science base: its interactive and integrative aspects build on, and add value to, research in other fields.

These linkages make it difficult to provide exact data for the UK expenditure for research on, or relevant to, global environmental change. The Research Councils estimate their combined current expenditure on GER to be around £47m per year, with a total UK GER spend of around £181m (\$271m) per year. The total figure may seem high, but it includes much research that also serves other purposes, such as coastal protection, energy efficiency and satellite sensor development (for further breakdown, see Section 4).

To put UK funding in an international context, estimated annual GER expenditures elsewhere are around \$260m in France, \$420m in Germany, \$690m in Japan and \$1800m in the USA (1995 data, including space-based observational programmes). Furthermore, even on conservative estimates, the potential impacts of climate change alone have financial consequences that are orders of magnitude higher. The research costs therefore have similarities to defence expenditure, safeguarding environmental security by avoiding or countering threats.

BOX 1. Defining the scope of GER

Global environmental research (GER) seeks to understand the processes of the integrated Earth system in order to: (i) identify, explain and predict anthropogenic changes in the global environment, in the context of natural variability; (ii) assess the potential regional and local impacts of those changes on natural and human systems, including their implications for international policy and law; and (iii) assist in developing appropriate responses.

This usage is consistent with previous terminology developed by IACGEC. Reference to the integrated Earth system focuses attention on perturbations occurring throughout global compartments and distribution systems; for example, changes affecting planetary heat distribution (via greenhouse gases and aerosols, and ocean and atmospheric dynamics), the large-scale natural cycles of materials (water, nutrients and key elements), and other global properties important for natural and managed ecosystems, and human well-being (such as stratospheric ozone depletion). Changes within more discrete spatial domains may gain global importance by their cumulative impact (e.g. changes in coastal systems, that have particular importance for many biogeochemical cycles and for human habitation).

Reference to international policy and law emphasises that GER problems cannot be adequately resolved by national governments, acting individually. On that basis, GER encompasses research relating to the exploitation of global commons' resources, beyond the jurisdiction of any national state (e.g. open ocean fish stocks, and the environmental impact of world trade systems). However, geographically wide replication of an environmental problem does not necessarily make it a GER issue: problems that can be satisfactorily addressed at the local or national level include urban litter, and industrial emissions with near-source impacts.

The concept of GER is still evolving. Fine-tuning of its boundaries can occur through new knowledge (e.g. recognising the radiative importance of atmospheric aerosols) or by the cumulative build-up of initially discrete effects. The latter process typically involves the crossing of a series of thresholds, whereby a specific environmental problem becomes no longer tractable at local, national or regional levels. Instead it becomes the subject of international policy initiatives, requiring global-scale attention at the intergovernmental level (e.g. biodiversity, desertification and deforestation). Whilst the growth of the human population, and rising per capita consumption, are clearly of fundamental importance in causing global environmental change, the inclusion of all research on these topics would make the scope of GER unmanageably large. The emphasis here is therefore on the large-scale interactions between human society and environmental systems, and the development of appropriate responses to ensure sustainable development at the global scale.

Public expenditure in the UK is currently under considerable pressure. The level of national GER effort should nevertheless be at least maintained, since:

- There is increasing awareness of the vulnerability of human well-being to environmental variability, in both the developed and developing world (e.g. recent droughts within the UK, and a halving of global grain stocks since 1987).
- There is strong scientific evidence that human-induced climate change is now occurring, with such effects likely to intensify in the next 50 years (IPCC 1996).

- We have an imperfect understanding of the non-climatic environmental consequences of projected increases in human population, per capita consumption and global economic trade, and their implications for the future availability of natural resources.
- Improvements have recently been made in the international coordination of GER (e.g. via the International Council of Scientific Unions, ICSU, and UN-related initiatives such as the Climate Agenda), providing added value to national efforts.
- Public concern for environmental issues remains high; however, there is considerable

scope to raise scientific understanding and improve the mechanisms whereby research results are made available for wider debate.

1.1.2 GER characteristics

Global environmental research is not just the scaling-up of existing modes of investigation. Instead, both the natural and social science components of GER require a new outlook, based on the following features of the research and its goals:

Spatial scales. An important longterm aim for GER is to provide geographically-specific predictions of the effects of global environmental change. This information is needed because global change impacts are not uniformly distributed. Yet in most cases the changes are driven by the cumulative effects of many processes operating on a worldwide basis: their study therefore requires global datasets and modelling, with associated requirements for international protocols for data gathering, management, exchange and analysis.

Temporal scales. Much GER effort is directed at developing predictive capability on a seasonal to multi-decadal scale. Fine-scale temporal variability is also important, since many significant impacts of climate change arise from extreme events, or subtle changes in seasonal timing. In addition, the geologically-recent past provides unique opportunities for testing models, and determining the stability (and instability) of natural systems.

Complexity. Traditional scientific approaches are mainly reductionist, emphasising linear relationships and steady state conditions. Such methodologies can be inappropriate for the complex, multifactorial linkages involved in global change. Highly interactive systems are typically resilient to external perturbation until a threshold is reached; after that, a rapid change in system state may occur. The possibility of such behaviour demands caution not only with regard to predictions of future global change (see below), but also in the design and advocacy of 'technological fixes' involving large-scale environmental manipulations: their net effect may be very different from the one intended.

Uncertainty. Because of the multi-system nature of global change, there will always be

uncertainties regarding long-range environmental forecasts. Hence, recognising and addressing uncertainty is a key theme of all GER issues. The aim of GER is therefore not a single exact prediction, but to replace ignorance by knowledge, to quantify risks where this is possible or meaningful, and to ensure that the limits of knowledge are properly reflected in discussion. Such information can then be used to explore and develop appropriate policy options, through the assessment of possible outcomes and their effects on people's lives.

1.1.3 GER components

The conceptual framework used for subsequent consideration of the UK strategy for global environmental research is shown in Figure 1. This framework, the GER triad, is based on the following main components or perspectives:

- *Human systems* that include industrial activities and impacts, human population processes, health, institutional structures, perceptions and values, and other aspects of socio-economic organisations and behaviour.
- *Physico-chemical systems* that include all the physical and chemical aspects of climate and other non-living processes operating in air, soil, surface water, groundwater and oceans.
- *Biological systems* that cover the range from molecular genetics to ecosystems, both natural and managed.

Each of these can act as driver of a global environmental change, by affecting one or both of the other components; each can also be impacted upon, and can bring about direct and indirect responses. Furthermore, all three components have their own internal dynamics, with properties and characteristics linked to other systems, not generally regarded as part of the global change ensemble.

The triad framework represents a considerable simplification of "real world" events. For example, it does not do justice to the role of chemical processes as the link between biological and physical systems. Nevertheless, this conceptual approach has several features that assist in analysing the causes and consequences of global environmental change, and defining

Fig. 1 Components of global environmental change

priorities for the national GER effort. Key aspects of the GER triad are as follows:

- It shows the complementarity of the different ways of tackling global change problems, whilst avoiding dominance by any one perspective.
- It emphasises the inter-relationships between processes, impacts and responses (including feedback effects), and the inherent multi-disciplinarity of Earth system science.
- It indicates where such linkages occur. First, within the human, physico-chemical and biological components, each component itself covering many scientific areas and disciplines; secondly, interactions between pairs of components; and thirdly, overarching properties and behaviour of the system as a whole, involving all components. Important research issues relating to these three linkage levels are considered in Section 2.

1.2 Relevance to national needs

1.2.1 UK policy for science, engineering and technology

National research policy is currently directed at improving economic performance, public services

and the quality of life, with emphasis on the role of partnerships to achieve these aims. This strategy was developed in the 1993 White Paper on Science, Engineering and Technology (SET), and is being carried forward by the Technology Foresight Programme. Environmental science features strongly in the 1995 Technology Foresight recommendations (Table 1), with an IACGEC paper included in the Report of the Agriculture, Natural Resources and Environment Panel (Progress through Partnership; Vol 11, Annex D). Other recent national policy documents relevant to the development of GER include the 1990 Environmental Strategy, the 1994 Sustainable Development Strategy, and the 1994 Report under the Framework Convention on Climate Change.

Research on global environmental change is highly relevant to the generic SET policy goals of wealth creation and quality of life. Environmental assets have real value, even if they are apparently 'free'; for example, air and water quality, soil fertility, terrestrial, freshwater and marine biodiversity, and the wide range of natural systems involved in waste assimilation, climate processes and nutrient cycles. From an environmental perspective, sustainable development requires the balancing of Gross National Product (GNP) increases with changes in natural capital, comprising the stock of environmental assets (at

Table 1 - Phase 1 Technology Foresight generic priorities relevant to GER issues

Panel		Priority
A Steering Group	i	Risk assessment and management
	ii	Modelling, simulation and prediction of complex systems and events including coastal and deep water environments
	iii	Clean processing technology, energy technology, environmentally sustainable technology, product and manufacturing life cycle analysis
B Agriculture, Natural Resources and Environment	i	Promote environmental research programmes encompassing the monitoring, surveillance and forecasting of environmental change, including the use of robotics and remote sensor & surveillance systems; development of associated baseline databases and information systems
	ii	Predictive modelling in the presence of uncertainty; associated process studies; forecasting and prediction of climate, geological & other environmental phenomena; hazard warning
	iii	Encourage efficient exploitation & where appropriate sustainable utilisation of natural resources
	iv	Promote impact evaluation methods such as environmental risk assessment, economic valuation and life cycle analysis
	v	Introduce improved technology for utilising forest products
	vi	Support research into wild fish conservation and aquaculture
	vii	Increase coordination and transfer, from fundamental research to the primary producer, processor, retailer and consumer to improve efficiency and uptake of new technologies
C Chemicals		Long term issue - meeting environmental requirements and taking advantage of environmental opportunities
D Construction		Social and environmental consequences of development: programme on information and techniques for whole life assessment of constructed facilities
E Energy	i	Develop a cheap thin film material for building structures to obtain photovoltaic power generation
	ii	Demonstrate clean coal power generation technologies
	iii	Develop energy efficient buildings
	iv	Long term issues - Environmental concerns about emissions, global warming, renewables
F Food and Drink		Exploit the growing capability of biotechnology to modify the properties of agricultural products
G Information Technology & Electronics		Promote the availability of high performance computing systems to researchers and developers
H Materials	i	High temperature and weight saving materials, sensors and modelling
	ii	Materials and processes which improve the environment and improve health care, including clean processing and biomaterials
I Transport	i	Long term issues - environmental regulation and balancing access and mobility with transport capacity and environmental constraints
	ii	Vehicles with greater efficiency and reduced environmental impact - The Foresight Vehicle environmentally friendly with no compromise on safety, performance or cost
	iii	Improved understanding and management of transport infrastructure

either the national or international level). As indicated above, many of these assets may not be directly subject to market pricing: their economic value only becomes apparent when remedial measures are needed, or when critical environmental functions are disrupted.

GER provides usable 'intelligence' on the properties, benefits and availability of global-scale environmental assets, and how they can be best managed to maximise long-term improvements in living standards. Economically important aspects include the future supply of natural resources, processes and services; the analysis of environmental externalities caused by market and policy failures (e.g. due to the lack of markets, inadequate protection of property and personal rights, or inappropriate government intervention); and guidance on the actions that may be needed to reduce the risk of large-scale and irreversible changes in the behaviour of natural systems.

The development of partnerships, that bring together different interests, is essential for GER - not only between Research Councils, and between research groups with different expertise and facilities (both nationally and internationally), but also between researchers and the user community. For GER, end users comprise the public (whose longterm interests should primarily be represented through national and local government departments and agencies), business and industry, intergovernmental bodies, and a range of national and international non-governmental organisations.

1.2.2 Economic relevance

GER is highly relevant to many economic sectors (Table 2). Changes in average environmental conditions have most implications for energy-related industries (including transport), and the agriculture, water and human health sectors. Changes in the frequency of extreme weather are more pervasive in their effects: insurance claims indicate their importance, with national totals frequently exceeding £500m for a single anomalous event (e.g. severe storm, flood, drought or extreme cold).

Understandably, most public interest is directed at how global change will affect our immediate environment. Nevertheless, the nature of modern economies requires that wider perspectives are

also taken into account. For example, the food producing and processing industries are increasingly sensitive to environmental changes on a worldwide basis, via effects on commodity prices, and the insurance and underwriting business similarly operates on the global scale. For the financial sector generally, investment efficiency over very long time horizons is important, for example with regard to pension funds. There is also a large, and rapidly growing, global market for clean technologies and other environmentally related goods and services (estimated at \$210 billion in 1992, and predicted to be \$510 billion by 2010).

Other ways in which GER can both safeguard wealth and directly contribute to wealth creation are by increased efficiency in the use of energy and raw materials; prior awareness of new environmental regulations (particularly at the European or international levels); and stimulation of technological and managerial innovation.

1.3 International context

1.3.1 Political, legal and developmental relevance

Joint action on an international basis is needed to develop an effective response to global change problems. The strong UK research base (in both social and natural sciences) has, to date, permitted a very significant national input to the formulation of environmental treaties and obligations - helping to ensure that such agreements are well-founded and serve our national interest. We are now party to several hundred international environmental obligations and arrangements, both at regional level (European Community legislation) and on a global basis. The latter group includes:

- The Montreal Protocol (1987), relating to the phase-out of ozone-depleting gases.
- The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC, established 1988 under WMO and UNEP), with Working Groups on scientific assessment, impacts and socio-economic issues.
- The UN Framework Convention on Climate Change, Convention on Biodiversity, Convention on Combatting Desertification, and Agenda 21,

Table 2 - Economic sectors that benefit from GER results

Food and agriculture; forestry and fishing	Climate predictions at a range of time scales; other global change impacts on the productivity of natural and managed ecosystems (including CO ₂ fertilization, UV-B damage, climate-related pests and diseases, and changes in soil fertility and ocean circulation); biotechnological and genetic aspects
Energy and transport	Implications of GER for energy policy, particularly re carbon cycle and fossil fuel use; assessment of impacts of aircraft pollution
Water resources and quality	Prediction of changes in precipitation, evaporation and water chemistry using climatic and hydrogeochemical models; land-use changes; sea level rise (re coastal groundwater)
Insurance and banking	Risk analysis for extreme events, subsidence, historical pollution and long-term trends; sea level rise; efficient investment in vulnerable regions and energy technologies
Building and construction (incl coastal engineering and flood/erosion defence)	Frequency of extreme events; long-term climate change; sea level rise
Chemical, pharmaceutical and biotechnology industries	GEC effects of new products; biodiversity (re gene pool and range of bio-processes)
Pollution abatement, clean technologies, and waste management	Implications of GER for emission control strategies; product life-cycle environmental audits
Remote sensing and other instrumentation	Earth observation by satellites and other automated 'smart' systems; software development and data management
Defence	Environmental security; ocean and atmosphere dynamics, sea ice; remote sensing and data management technologies
Health	Improved knowledge of effects of air and water quality, and UV-B, and of climate-related diseases, stresses and trauma
Tourism and leisure	Effects of long-term changes in climate, sea level, coastal morphology, landscape, air, soil and water quality; biodiversity (re eco-tourism)
Climate prediction and environmental consultancy services	Routine use of global-scale observational, data management and modelling techniques, for regional and local impact assessment studies in relation to baseline levels

all arising from the UN Conference on Environment and Development (UNCED, 1992).

- The work of the UN Commission on Sustainable Development, the UN Development Programme, the UN Environment Programme, and subsidiary intergovernmental bodies (e.g. the Global Environment Facility).

Many other international negotiations and agreements (e.g. GATT, the General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade) have important environmental implications, affecting the rate and geographical pattern of resource exploitation. A substantial effort is required not only to implement successfully these agreements at the national and global levels, but also to maintain an influential UK role in their further development (through IPCC, UNCED and EC processes, and via other bodies).

In addition, the viability of global agreements on environmental issues is critically dependent on the capability of other countries to undertake research, contribute to the policy debate, and ensure effective implementation. This situation makes it inappropriate for the UK to place strict national limits on its science goals of wealth creation and quality of life. Opportunities for capacity building in the GER context require further attention by UK funding agencies, linking with existing ODA, OECD, EC and Commonwealth initiatives. Such collaborative work would seem to be of particular value if directed at enhancing environmental management capabilities in developing countries that are either most vulnerable to global change impacts, or are most important for the implementation of key conventions.

1.3.2 International research programmes

The existence of GER expertise in the UK greatly enhances our ability to participate in, and benefit from, relevant research activities and policy initiatives at the international level. Relationships with international GER projects and programmes are of increasing importance due to:

- The emphasis given to international scientific coordination and collaboration by the 1993 White Paper (Chapter 6), with particular regard to high cost facilities.

- The similar recommendations, with specific regard to global change research, by the 1993

OECD Mega Science Forum and by the International Group of Funding Agencies for Global Change Research (IGFA).

- The development of the Climate Agenda by the World Climate Programme, establishing internationally-agreed objectives and priorities for climate research and operational services.

- The increasing importance of EC funding (and links with European partners) for the support of UK research in natural and social sciences.

Annex 4 identifies relevant international research programmes with UK involvement. Two programmes have been especially effective in stimulating the development of GER work: the World Climate Research Programme (WCRP, under WMO, IOC and ICSU) and the International Geosphere-Biosphere Programme (IGBP, under ICSU). The UK has strong, yet selective, involvement in the scientific leadership and implementation of these programmes. Information on the closely-related development of global observation systems is given in Section 3.3.

A third GER-directed programme, the International Human Dimensions of Global Environmental Change Programme (IHDP), provides potential for greater international coordination of complementary work on socio-economic aspects of global change. IHDP was initiated by the International Social Science Council (ISSC); its co-sponsorship by ICSU has recently been agreed, and its structure and objectives are currently under review.

The European Commission's Research and Development Framework IV Programme (1994-98) gives high priority to GER, with relevant funding areas on Natural Environment, Environmental Quality and Global Change; Environmental Technologies; and Human Dimensions of Environmental Change. The UK has been particularly successful in these areas: out of 235 contracts recently approved, 149 (63%) have at least one UK partner.

2. Key research issues

2.1 General aspects

In the Sections that follow, key research issues for UK GER are identified in generic terms. A comprehensive overview of all aspects of global environmental change is not attempted; instead attention is focussed on themes and topics that not only have high scientific and strategic importance, but are also regarded as especially relevant to UK research capabilities. Thus the omission of a specific research activity does not necessarily mean that it is scientifically unimportant.

Three groups of research issues are considered, based on the triad framework (Fig 2):

- *Underpinning Research* that primarily concerns a single component (Section 2.2). This research builds on single-discipline studies, that provide the fundamental knowledge base; however, many aspects are inherently multidisciplinary, and may already involve a wide range of scientific interactions and collaborations, both within the natural and social sciences.

- *Interactive Research* that involves multidisciplinary linkages mainly occurring between two components (Section 2.3). The emergence of these themes and topics indicates that GER is moving to a more mature phase in its development. However, attention needs to be given to their progress, and some topics may require either stimulation or coordination over the next 5 - 10 years.

- *Systemic Research* that spans all components of the triad (Section 2.4). Issues identified here are the overarching 'grand challenges' for our understanding of the Earth system. Whilst aspects may have already been covered, as either underpinning or interactive research, there is an increasing need for the global problems to be addressed in an integrated manner. This has important implications for strategic planning, inter-agency coordination and long-term support.

All three levels of GER are necessary. Major uncertainties and new scientific issues continue to emerge in the underpinning category, and satisfactory attention to these issues is the foundation for evolving and maturing work in the

interactive and systemic categories. All three components offer exciting scientific challenges which will depend upon the future availability of bright young scientists. The scientific significance of most of the themes and topics identified here has previously been recognised, since there is either ongoing work supported by one or more of the UK funding agencies, or future support is committed in Forward Look documentation (see Section 4). Consideration has also been given to research areas important to the UK GER effort that are currently underfunded, either because they are new scientific growth areas, or because former strengths have been relatively neglected.

The relationship between the GER issues identified here and the environmental priorities of the Technology Foresight exercise are shown in Annex 2, together with the match to relevant economic sectors.

2.2 Underpinning research

2.2.1 Human systems

The human systems component of GER comprises social, economic and medical research directed at environmental issues, and the development of environmentally-friendly technologies. Such research addresses the basic questions of why and how global environmental change matters to individuals and society. Four fundamental themes can be distinguished: improving our understanding of the anthropogenic drivers of global environmental change; assessing the impacts of such change on human society; assisting in the development of cost effective and viable responses; and investigating the ways in which knowledge on global environmental change is translated into action.

Ongoing research in all these areas is required because human systems are dynamic, and the nature of global change problems is evolving. A specific UK effort is needed because much of the empirical work, such as the valuation of environmental assets, is dependent on the cultural setting. The UK has great strengths in many areas (e.g. environmental economics), and is closely

involved in international policy development relating to global environmental change. Furthermore, there are wider political and ethical interests in human development, population issues and resource management.

Priority issues for socio-economic GER include:

- *The relationship between industry (including agriculture) and the environment.* For example: how can businesses improve their environmental performance while remaining competitive? What is the relationship between technological innovation and the environmental impacts of products and processes? How do businesses relate to other groups with an interest in the environment (consumers, the public, government and regulatory agencies)?
- *Perceptions, attitudes, ethics and behaviour* of the public towards the global environment, as citizens and consumers. Related areas include the need for mutual communication and understanding of scientific issues and findings concerning global change, particularly where there appears to be a disparity between scientific and public perception; the need for improved understanding on the nature of public perceptions and attitudes, including a historical perspective; also the role of education, and participation in non-governmental organisations and other environmental initiatives.
- *Methodologies for assessing environmental damage* and for sustainably managing resource systems need to be refined and applied. Among the relevant techniques are economic evaluation, risk analysis, multi-criterion assessment techniques, life-cycle analysis, and eco-design principles. User needs with respect to these techniques are currently poorly defined.
- *Policy development processes*, including legal and economic aspects. Work is needed on the design of efficient policy instruments (regulatory measures, economic incentives and voluntary agreements); institutional arrangements for policy making; information and assessment needs; and the role of scientific knowledge in informing and guiding policy.
- *The role of international agreements and institutions.* We have an inadequate understanding of the factors affecting the worldwide development, implementation and enforcement of

international environmental commitments; the effectiveness of international institutions; or the links with domestic policies. Research is also required on the environmental impact of other international regimes (such as those relating to trade) and the role of national interests, political movements, NGOs, international institutions, and knowledge-based communities. These issues need to be addressed from a variety of disciplinary perspectives, including politics, economics, law, international relations and sociology, as well as through interdisciplinary work.

The underpinning research in medical science includes much basic work on *epidemiology* and *human fertility*. There is need to investigate how a wide suite of environmental factors may be influencing national, regional (European) and global variations in human health. These factors include air and water quality, different climatic regimes, climate variation, and changing settlement patterns. Research priorities directly relating to the impacts of global environmental change on human health are considered under Section 2.3.

There needs to be continued research effort to develop more efficient *technologies for emission abatement*, particularly for greenhouse gases. While such work also serves to reduce pollution at the local level, the widespread adoption of cleaner technologies is a necessary part of the response to global environmental threats. Examples of such developments include alternatives to fossil fuels, such as solar cells, and technologies for the more efficient use of energy and the minimisation of waste, through recycling, re-use and recovery. Such work is closely linked to: energy and transport policies (e.g. in trying to make cities more sustainable); scenarios for anthropogenic emissions of greenhouse gases and radiatively-active aerosols; and other aspects of air quality.

A closely related topic is work on the *cost effectiveness of energy efficiency measures* in the domestic, public and commercial sectors, in order to determine the feasibility of future emission abatement policies. Recent results for CO₂ indicate that around half the energy efficiency measures currently available provide direct financial savings, regardless of any wider benefits in the context of global change. Options for the disposal and storage of anthropogenic CO₂ are considered under Section 2.3.

Fig.2 Research issues in relation to the GER triad.
 Blue - Underpinning Research; Green - Interactive Research; Red - Systemic Research

2.2.2 Physico-chemical systems

The physico-chemical component of the Earth system encompasses the physics and chemistry of the atmosphere, hydrosphere (marine and freshwater), cryosphere and the geochemically-mobile lithosphere. It therefore includes the physical climate, i.e. the ensemble of atmospheric and oceanic circulations, and their physical and chemical states.

To understand the physico-chemical system it is necessary to quantify very many processes and phenomena occurring over a wide range of scales, from molecular to global. The observations, understanding and modelling of the component parts has now reached the stage at which coupled models of atmospheric physics and chemistry, and of atmospheric and oceanic physics, are producing interesting and useful results. However, there are still major errors and uncertainties, even in the most basic parameters and on the largest spatial and temporal scales. To reduce these uncertainties requires well coordinated global data-gathering and modelling, as well as experimental studies in the field and in the laboratory.

Priority issues for physico-chemical GER include:

- *Natural variability of atmosphere, ocean and soil* on timescales from seasons to decades. This variability provides the background against which anthropogenic change must be assessed, and a major test for models that are being developed for climate change prediction. If aspects of natural variability can be shown to be predictable, that would have great economic and social significance. The need is for continuing observations, to give improvements in the data and process descriptions used for modelling of the separate and coupled systems.

- *Development of atmosphere-ocean general circulation models.* Such models play a central role in studies of natural variability and of anthropogenic climate change. However, there is insufficient knowledge of their behaviour. Currently almost all coupled models drift away from the observed climate unless a large adjustment is made between the heat flux leaving the ocean and entering the atmosphere: this is an indication of problems in the models.

- *The radiative behaviour of the atmosphere* and its inclusion in climate models. In particular,

better representations are needed of water vapour and clouds. Water vapour is the dominant greenhouse gas, and yet its distribution in space and time is poorly understood. Cooling effects due to anthropogenic sulphur aerosols are currently represented by changes in land surface reflectance: such effects need to be explicitly in the atmosphere, with account also taken of direct (cooling) and indirect effects (e.g. on cloud droplet size) of a variety of other aerosols.

- *The atmospheric chemistry of climatically important gases.* The next generation of climate models need to include the effects of chemical reactions in the lower atmosphere, influencing the concentrations of methane, ozone, nitrogen oxides and aerosols. Processes occurring on particle surfaces and water droplets require further experimental study.

- *Land-ocean-atmosphere chemical exchanges.* Better information is required on the chemical exchanges (of greenhouse gases and aerosols) between the land, ocean and atmosphere, and the factors controlling these processes. Such data are needed to develop models of global biogeochemical cycles, and hence assess feedback effects during conditions of environmental change.

- *Stratospheric ozone and UV-B.* There is need for further modelling and monitoring studies of trace constituents in the stratosphere, also for laboratory work on heterogeneous reactions (occurring on particles) and homogeneous chemistry (photolytic processes). The relative importance of different ozone depletion processes needs to be determined, with emphasis on the integration of chemical models and physical transport processes. The transport of trace chemicals across the tropopause and in the lower stratosphere needs to be better understood.

- *Improved regional predictions, particularly for extreme events* are highly desirable; for example, the likelihood of intense tropical cycles, mid-latitude storms or severe late frosts at specific localities. However, it is necessary to develop more robust models of global-scale relationships before regional predictions of climatic behaviour can be given full credibility; furthermore, the non-linearity of extreme events requires a better understanding of weather systems and scale interactions, beyond that needed to model more normal behaviour.

■ Techniques for efficient *data assimilation* in models need to be developed further, so that maximum use can be made of GER-related observational data. Models should be used to determine optimal observational strategies.

In addition, attention needs to be given to *land surface processes*, since these play a vital role in climate models. The importance of biological aspects is now receiving increased attention; this topic is therefore covered as an interactive issue, under Section 2.3.3.

2.2.3 Biological systems

The survival of living organisms depends on their ability to withstand changing environmental conditions. Thus analysis of biological systems in the GER context draws on aspects from all life science disciplines, whether defined on the basis of scale (biochemistry, molecular biology, physiology, population biology and ecology), taxonomic groupings (microbiology, botany and zoology), habitat (terrestrial, freshwater and marine), or applications (agriculture, forestry and fishery sciences). In particular, Britain has a long and distinguished history of research on crop science and environmental biology, and it is important that current capabilities in these areas are retained and developed to address GER-related issues.

Relationships with external conditions have, to date, mostly been investigated on a single species basis. These studies are necessary and need to be continued; however, species interactions are what ultimately matter from a GER perspective. Thus we need to know how a particular environmental change might alter a molecular process (e.g. the rate of enzyme induction) or the physiological performance of a key species; we also need to know the significance of that effect, assessed in terms of the interactions between that species and others.

An environmental change may make an individual more vulnerable to disease, or may alter competitive balances, either in that species' favour or against it (depending on how other organisms are affected). The large-scale replication of such effects will alter relationships at the population level, changing community structure and function. Economic consequences will result if managed or harvested species are

directly or indirectly involved. There may also be significant impacts on biodiversity, nutrient cycles, and energy and water exchanges, with feedback effects on physico-chemical systems.

Ecological studies of species interactions provide the alternative approach to these problems. However, without knowledge of the underlying mechanisms at the individual and molecular level, such work is unable to make predictions outside the range of conditions studied. The two approaches therefore need to be brought together, with the overall aim of *strengthening research links between population ecologists and 'mechanism scientists'*, the latter having relevant expertise in molecular biology and physiology.

Other important underpinning GER issues for biological systems include:

■ *The functional role of biodiversity.* The key issue in the GER context is the relationship between ecosystem properties (e.g. productivity, resilience to stress) and community structure (not only in terms of species richness, but also foodweb complexity and pathways of resource use). Such studies are needed for marine, freshwater and terrestrial environments. Many reductions in biodiversity are closely related to intensification of land use: priorities for conservation therefore need to be based on realistic scenarios for future changes in land use and climate, and their potential interactions.

■ *The role of many biological processes in soils* in global change, including their effects on mineralisation rates, water movements and trace gas emissions. A much better understanding of the rate functions, stability and resilience of soil processes is needed to quantify the large-scale surface fluxes of water, heat and greenhouse gases (see 2.3.3), also to determine the effects of land use and land cover changes (including degradation, desertification and soil erosion). There are important opportunities here for soil scientists to interact with related disciplines; e.g. in the application of molecular biology techniques, and new modelling approaches.

■ *Transitional states of communities and ecosystems.* These will become of ever greater importance under conditions of increasing direct and indirect human impacts, as time lags develop between physical and chemical changes and the

full responses of biological systems. The properties of transitional ecosystems, and the timescales of change, therefore need to be better understood, for more realistic modelling of the effects of climate change on single species (crops and pests), community dynamics and biogeochemical cycles.

■ *Natural variability.* Biological systems are inherently highly variable in time and space, particularly in aquatic environments. Detection of human impacts and climate change effects requires better knowledge of the factors responsible for natural variability on interannual and decadal timescales relating such changes to shifts in physico-chemical conditions.

Research priorities relating to the interactions between managed ecosystems and global change, and the role of the biosphere in global-scale cycles are considered in Sections 2.3 and 2.4 respectively.

2.3 Interactive research

2.3.1 Global change impacts on health

Global environmental changes predicted for the next 20-50 years seem likely to have a net adverse effect on human health, both in the UK and on a worldwide basis. However, neither the nature of potential health impacts nor their associated socio-economic costs have been well-quantified. The relevant level of analysis of health risks is for populations or communities, rather than for individuals or small groups.

There is an urgent need for research to: identify the range of potential health impacts; carry out comparative studies in relation to existing environmental gradients; and develop predictive models for national, regional and global application. Both direct and indirect effects of global change on health can be anticipated: preliminary analyses indicate that indirect effects of climate change are likely to be the more important, arising from disturbances in natural systems and alterations in ecological relationships. All the aspects considered below would benefit from a multidisciplinary approach.

■ *Direct health effects of climate change.* Current climate models and existing health

statistics can be used to estimate, in simple terms, the direct impact of anticipated temperature changes on mortality and illness. However, there are limitations to this approach, particularly with regard to regional and local impacts, and the occurrence of extreme events with significant health effects (e.g. heatwaves). More sophisticated scenarios therefore need to be developed.

■ *Air and water quality effects.* Climate change would affect the frequency and severity of air pollution incidents; for example, through the enhanced production of photochemical pollutants (such as tropospheric ozone) at warmer temperatures. There are also likely to be changes in the abundance of biological materials (e.g. pollen, moulds and house mites) that may contribute to asthma and other aero-allergic disorders. Reductions in water availability during drought conditions affect its quality, and additional treatment may be necessary (e.g. if toxic algal blooms develop in reservoirs under low flow conditions).

■ The wider geographical *spread of warm climate diseases*, such as malaria, dengue, leishmaniasis and schistosomiasis. Whilst northern Europe is unlikely to be directly affected in the near future by these vector-borne diseases, there may be increased risks for inhabitants and travellers in other parts of the world. However, many food-borne and water-borne infective agents (e.g. including moulds and those causing enteric infections) also spread more readily in warmer and wetter conditions, with a close correlation between UK summer temperatures and food poisoning incidents.

■ *UV-B effects on human health.* Skin cancer is a main 'Health of the Nation' target: there is need for better information on UV exposure risks (episodic and cumulative), to assist in developing effective public health advice. Research should also address the impacts of increased ambient UV-B exposures on the incidence of other skin disorders, eye cataracts and immune-related diseases.

■ *Interactive effects of urbanization.* The rapid worldwide growth of cities will influence susceptibility to many global environmental change processes, and the patterns of their impacts. Such effects will interact with those

identified above. For example, the local severity of heatwaves is influenced by housing density, the latter creating urban 'heat islands'. There are also demographic influences on the transmission of vector-borne diseases, and on air, soil and water quality.

■ *Ecological epidemiology.* The assessment of global change impacts on human infectious diseases needs to be more closely linked to studies of health effects on livestock, and of pests and diseases affecting crop productivity, since similar principles should apply in each case. Thus there is considerable scope for worthwhile collaboration between research groups with expertise in the ecology of infectious disease (e.g. assessing control options should rabies become established in Britain) and conventional medical, veterinary, agricultural and geochemical approaches.

2.3.2 Global change impacts on agriculture, forestry and fisheries

Global-scale human population pressures will increase the demand for managed and harvested biological resources. Crops and forests will be subject to increased atmospheric CO₂, and significant changes in rainfall and temperature patterns are anticipated. Such environmental changes will have both positive and negative impacts: a wide range of scientific skills need to be deployed to take full advantage of the positive whilst minimising the negative consequences.

The UK has much relevant expertise, with proven abilities to transfer such knowledge and technologies to developing countries that might be more seriously threatened by global environmental change. Important research topics include:

■ *Adaptation in the agricultural sector.* The development of appropriate adaptive strategies could greatly limit the negative effects of climate change on agriculture (and could help to realise the advantages of any beneficial changes). Options include improved water management, changes in planting schedules, improved tillage and soil management systems, and changes in crops using biotechnology as well as conventional approaches. Assuming that reliable regional predictions become available, such developments should be able to keep pace with environmental change. But genetic manipulations, whether

achieved by novel or conventional means, can carry a cost: greater uniformity may increase vulnerability to 'unexpected' conditions (including pest and disease outbreaks), and such developments may also have socio-economic implications, especially for the farming systems of developing countries. GER interest in these topics therefore involves human geographers and social scientists, as well as molecular biologists, population ecologists and agriculturalists.

■ *Forestry and global change.* Trees grown for timber are less amenable to genetic manipulation to keep pace with environmental changes, on account of their long harvest cycle. Thus the best estimates of climatic conditions 20-50 years ahead are directly relevant to current planting policies. There are particular problems for the UK, where commercial forestry is highly dependent on non-native species (notably Sitka spruce and lodgepole pine) that are not grown under plantation conditions elsewhere in Europe. Although there is much UK research on silviculture and woodland ecology, there is insufficient on tree biology to adequately assess the effects of climate change.

■ *Marine living resources* are currently threatened more by human over-exploitation than by climate change. However, fishing impacts must be considered in the context of high natural variability in year-class success, affecting recruitment to the adult population. Relatively subtle changes in temperature and hydrodynamic regimes (acting via changes in plankton abundance) are responsible for 'poor' and 'good' years. The need is for an international policy framework to achieve sustainable catches, in ways that are both scientifically-sound and feasible. This requires a more integrated research approach, taking account of fishing practices (and how they are affected by regulations), natural variability and climate change scenarios.

■ *UV-B effects on crops and livestock.* Significant mid-latitude changes in stratospheric ozone levels would have the potential for UV-B impacts of considerable economic importance. However, dose/effect relationships are poorly understood under natural conditions. Laboratory studies on crop species indicate high inter-strain and inter-species variability in sensitivity: on that basis, biotechnology techniques and natural selection processes may, together, lessen the scale of deleterious impacts on food production.

Research issues relating to CO₂ fertilization effects are considered under 2.3.4 below.

2.3.3 Land surface properties and processes

Vertical exchanges of energy, water and trace gases at the land surface have important forcing and feedback effects on the global environment. Such processes are not currently well represented in global climate models, and we have inadequate knowledge of their general importance for biogeochemical cycles and soil/water relationships. The need is for a quantitative understanding of the near-surface physico-chemical and biological components of these fluxes, their interactions and further linkages - both with events in the overlying atmosphere and with basin-scale hydrological processes.

Most long-term environmental observations relate to the land surface: we need to understand how the atmosphere and land interact in order to be able to use these observations effectively, not only to detect change, but also to attribute the causes of such change. Research issues of particular importance include:

- *Upscaling and downscaling.* There is need for better representation and integration of processes occurring across a wide range of spatial (patch, landscape, regional, continental and global) and temporal (diurnal, seasonal and interannual) scales. In particular, improvements are needed in the way that global climate models can be related to local topographical conditions, through 'weather generators' and other down-scaling techniques.

- The incorporation of *biologically-mediated processes in surface exchange models.* For example, account needs to be taken of soil properties and microbiological processes; evapotranspiration from vegetation; the physiological responses of plants to changes in their environment (e.g. responses affecting the structure of canopies and the timing of their development); and interactions both with the atmospheric boundary layer and with the free atmosphere. Many of these effects have been quantified by ecologists and micro-meteorologists, but they have not yet been included in UK climate prediction models.

- *The use of remotely-sensed space observations* and regional baseline databases,

coupled to models, to understand the large scale factors affecting environmental geochemistry, land cover and productivity, and the links between terrestrial and atmospheric processes (particularly radiation feedbacks). For global scale studies, such methods are often the only source of consistent observations; also see Section 3.1.1

2.3.4 The carbon and nitrogen cycles

Carbon and nitrogen are elements of particular significance for global environmental change. Both are intimately involved in climate processes; furthermore, human activities have already greatly perturbed their global distributions and future changes, with uncertain impacts, seem inevitable.

Most climate change scenarios are based on increases in atmospheric CO₂, with the assumption that these atmospheric increases can be directly related to anthropogenic emissions. This approach does not take adequate account of the scale and variability of other processes that exchange CO₂ with the atmosphere. Through natural processes, both biological and physical, there are large fluxes of carbon into the air from land and sea, and in the reverse direction. The carbon added to the air due to fossil fuel combustion and other human activities is an anthropogenic perturbation to this natural carbon cycle. Currently, the net result is a build up of atmospheric carbon at a rate about half that suggested by the anthropogenic emissions alone, with the remainder being taken up by the oceans and the land biosphere.

There is a risk that such damping effects will themselves be disrupted by future climate change (as occurred naturally during the ice age cycle), so that in the future partitioning of man-made CO₂ between the atmosphere and other reservoirs may be different from what has been observed in the recent past. Hence, it is important to understand the natural dynamics of global carbon movements, including consideration of methane (CH₄) as well as CO₂. Key areas of uncertainty are as follows:

- *Terrestrial CO₂ fertilization effects* and their role in the 'missing carbon' problem (we know there is net uptake somewhere, but are unsure where). Laboratory studies show that elevated CO₂ levels can greatly benefit plant growth, giving increased drought resistance (particularly

for C₃ species). Field studies are less clear cut: other nutrients can then become limiting, and there may be decreases in leaf protein content (with food quality implications for humans, livestock and plant pests). Further experiments are needed to investigate these issues for natural and semi-natural systems.

■ Global change effects on the *ocean carbon cycle*. We now have a better understanding of the relative importance of biological and physico-chemical processes on present day ocean carbon fluxes. However, responses to future conditions (e.g. involving changes in ocean circulation patterns) cannot yet be quantified: models are limited by a lack of seasonal and spatial data, and by gaps in our knowledge of key processes (e.g. the role of trace nutrients, such as iron). New ocean colour satellites provide opportunities for major advances in the next 5-10 years.

■ The feasibility, cost-effectiveness and ecological consequences of direct *carbon storage or enhanced natural uptake*, to mitigate CO₂ increases. Underground storage or deep sea disposal provide the main options for the former; forestation or, more controversially, open ocean fertilization are possibilities for the latter approach.

■ The dynamics of natural and anthropogenic *methane (CH₄) sinks and sources* are still poorly known, for terrestrial and marine environments, and in relation to atmospheric oxidation processes. The UK has a specific need for better data on CH₄ emissions from landfill sites, and for models that relate CH₄ fluxes to climate impacts and land use changes (particularly for coastal wetlands and waterlogged upland soils).

Human perturbations of the nitrogen cycle are not generally perceived as an environmental threat. However, nitrous oxide (N₂O) is the third most important greenhouse gas, and changes in many nitrogen fluxes have been proportionately greater than for carbon. The anthropogenic fixation of atmospheric nitrogen (in fertilizer production, combustion processes and by growing leguminous crops) now exceeds natural fixation processes (by soil and marine microorganisms, and via lightning). Key GER issues relating to the nitrogen cycle include:

■ Quantification of *human-driven changes in nitrogen transformation processes*. For

example, recent global estimates of N₂O production due to nitrate and ammonium fertilizers are highly uncertain, ranging from 0.01 - 2.2 TgN per year; effects of soil type, temperature and farming practices are all important, but have yet to be adequately investigated.

■ Analysis of the *atmospheric role of reactive nitrogen compounds*. For example, the importance of NO_x in enhancing ozone formation in the lower atmosphere, and of N₂O in causing ozone breakdown in the upper atmosphere (both effects having undesirable consequences from a human perspective).

■ The impact of *enhanced atmospheric inputs of nitrogen* on terrestrial and marine ecosystems. Preliminary estimates indicate that such inputs are increasing the net global carbon uptake in the biosphere by around 0.5 GtC per year (10% of fossil fuel emissions). These effects are likely to have a threshold, and we do not know when that will be reached.

2.3.5 Changes in coastal systems

Coastal land and shelf seas cover only a small part of the Earth's surface, yet play a vital role for human settlement, for our use of living and non-living natural resources, and as the main interface between key Earth system compartments (land, sea, air and freshwater) involved in global change.

For the UK, coastal systems support a particularly wide diversity of environmental functions and services; their management, and responses to global change impacts, are therefore of special interest. Recent funding initiatives have greatly improved the national integration of land-ocean environmental research.

GER-related research needs are: first, to widen that interdisciplinarity, through joint work between social and natural scientists; second, to extend the geographical perspective, so that national problems are viewed in their regional and global contexts; and third, to address the scientific uncertainties relating to sea level rise. Specific research issues include:

■ *Valuation of environmental assets* for the various uses of coastal systems. There is urgent need for well-designed comparisons of the costs and benefits of different policy options

(precaution, protection, sustainable management and restoration), and to improve the weighting of economic instruments for management purposes.

■ The development of *effective legal and administrative regimes* for coastal zone management. Conventionally structured laws and institutional arrangements often fail to reflect fully the distinctive demands and significance of coastal systems, on both a national and international basis.

■ *Assimilative capacity, water quality, biogeochemical and sedimentation effects.* Quantitative assessments are needed of the capacity of coastal waters to receive and process contaminants (from fertilizers, sewage, industrial waste, and atmospheric inputs), and their effects on water quality, transformation and re-concentration processes, the productivity of shelf seas, trace gas exchanges and the export of dissolved and particulate materials to the open ocean.

■ Integrated analysis of *absolute sea level rise*, to improve predictions of future impacts through process studies and modelling work. There is need to bring together UK expertise in global monitoring of sea level change with complementary capabilities in geodesy, altimetry, cryology, hydrology, geology, sedimentology and climate modelling.

■ Integrated analysis of *relative sea level change, coastal erosion and coastal flooding* including sedimentological aspects and socio-economic analyses of coastal defence strategies - both hard (engineered) and soft (dunes and wetlands) - and of managed retreat. Much research on coastal engineering is independent of global change considerations; however, that work becomes increasingly important if, as seems likely, the UK coast becomes subject to significant sea level rise.

2.3.6 Past global changes

In order to have confidence in predictions of future global changes, we need to test our understanding of Earth system behaviour under a range of different conditions. The diverse combinations of circumstances that have occurred in the geologically-recent past provide that

opportunity. Previous global environmental changes also provide novel insights on cause and effect relationships for the natural factors involved, identifying significant processes that are not yet included in models of climate dynamics or biogeochemical behaviour.

Two time-scales are of particular research interest:

■ The *Quaternary ice age cycles*. There have been large and frequently rapid changes in temperature, atmospheric composition, land and sea ice cover, ocean circulation and productivity, and the distribution of terrestrial ecosystems over the past 500,000 years. These aspects have mostly been studied independently, on a descriptive basis; there is now need for integrative analyses to improve our understanding of forcing functions (orbital changes, greenhouse gases and switches in ocean circulation), temporal dependences, ecological impacts and feedback responses.

■ The past 2000 years. Recent climate changes have been less dramatic, but can be matched more closely (e.g. seasonally and annually, using tree rings, layered lake sediments and written records) with other environmental changes, including volcanic activity and solar variations. Research is needed on the geographic scale of climatic anomalies, their interaction with natural systems and human development, and the role of human activity as a driver of both climatic and non-climatic environmental change.

2.4 Systemic research

2.4.1 Integrated climate studies

In the context of Earth system behaviour, climate means more than a statistical description of meteorological conditions: processes and effects are also involved. That wider meaning was recognised in the UN Framework Convention on Climate Change (FCCC), with its ultimate objective being "...the stabilization of greenhouse gas concentrations in the atmosphere at a level that would prevent dangerous anthropogenic interference with the climate system. Such a level should be achieved within a time frame sufficient to allow ecosystems to adapt naturally to climate change, to ensure that food production is not threatened and to enable economic development to proceed in a sustainable manner".

The FCCC goal is in accordance with climate-related research developments during the past decade, their future national direction (as indicated here), and their international assessment (through the IPCC process) and alignment (via the Climate Agenda, and ICSU programmes). A sequential expansion of conceptual boundaries, capabilities and applications is involved. The main phases, graded from what has been achieved to what has yet to be done, are as follows:

- i) The development of general circulation models that simulate atmospheric physics at the global scale. Main uses: problem identification and theoretical understanding; forecasting on time scales upto months.
- ii) The inclusion of variability in ocean and land surface conditions, through coupled interactions with other models (based on energy and water exchanges). Main uses: global-scale impact assessments, general policy guidance and theoretical understanding; forecasting on time scales upto years.
- iii) The inclusion of variability in radiative processes, by simulating the distribution patterns, and interactions, of chemical species in the atmosphere. Main uses: signal detection, global and regional-scale impact assessments, and refining policy guidance.
- iv) The inclusion of interactive biological effects, primarily via marine and terrestrial components of the carbon cycle. Also the testing of global climate models against palaeoclimate regimes; and advanced data assimilation, using Earth observation data. Main uses: aiding detailed policy formulation at global, regional and national scales.
- v) The inclusion of interactive socio-economic behaviour. For example, with climate-induced changes in agriculture affecting economic structures, and linked to large-scale changes in demography and industrial performance. Such models will provide scenarios, not predictions; nevertheless, they are more realistic (and hence more useful) than those that lack the capability for human responses to co-evolve with changes in environmental conditions.

Models of various scales and structures are needed to achieve the above developments, with associated studies in many different scientific fields. By comparing results from a variety of

approaches at national and international levels, differences between models will help identify their weaknesses, either in data supply or in their representations of fundamental processes. These inadequacies can then be rectified - through targeted data gathering or research - in an iterative manner. No single model, however sophisticated, can exactly mimic the real world: the need is to develop models with minimum complexity that nevertheless provide a satisfactory simulation of the behaviour of the features of interest. Furthermore, the differing public perceptions of what constitutes a "dangerous" level of interference with the climate system may be impossible to accommodate within a single numeric model. An overall aim of integrated climate studies must be to maximise the benefit obtained from the available information, but not necessarily in a single synthesis.

2.4.2 Biogeochemical cycles

Around 25 chemical elements are required for biological processes. During the past 3000 million years, natural geochemical processes and the actions of living organisms have changed the chemical form and distributions of these elements at the Earth's surface, assisted by atmospheric and oceanic transport systems. Within the past 300 years, human activities have further altered the rates of many of these transformation and redistribution processes, mobilising additional elements and introducing many new compounds into the environment. The climate changes that are likely in the next 30 years are but one of many manifestations of these geochemical perturbations.

The global movements and chemical forms of elements are closely connected to energy exchanges and water-driven processes. From a physical viewpoint, fluid dynamics is particularly important; from a chemical perspective, oxidation/reduction reactions in the atmosphere, and those relating to pH changes in aqueous systems, are of special interest. In biological terms, the main linkages between elements relate to their role as plant nutrients, their packaging in organic compounds, and microbiological breakdown processes. The human involvement in biogeochemical cycles is more diverse: it can be indirect (acting by changing the rate of natural processes) or direct (mobilising materials, changing their chemistry and releasing them, particularly by combustion).

A generic research strategy to assess the significance of human activities on global biogeochemical cycles requires, for the element(s) of interest:

- i) Quantification of the amounts occurring as mobile reservoirs, in different chemical forms, in the major global compartments (ocean, atmosphere and land surface). Such data are now reasonably well known for most key elements.
- ii) Quantification of global transport pathways, including the main natural fluxes between compartments. Exchanges into and out of the atmosphere are particularly important, on account of chemical mixing and distribution processes, and the possibility of climate-linked effects.
- iii) Representation of the biogeochemical factors controlling these fluxes. Process studies (both field and laboratory) are needed to quantify these relationships; techniques include the use of isotopes as source markers.
- iv) Determination of anthropogenic fluxes, and their interactions with natural processes. The former is relatively straightforward; the latter more difficult.
- v) Integrated impact analysis and prediction of future behaviour, using the information and relationships determined through (i) - (iv).

These are all major tasks. As indicated in Section 2.3.4, much current effort is directed at the global cycles of carbon and nitrogen: progress has been made, but many aspects have yet to be satisfactorily resolved. One general finding is that the pathways of these elements are closely connected, mostly through biological processes; in addition, there are many linkages with the mobilisation of phosphorus, sulphur and iron.

It is neither feasible nor desirable for every research group addressing element cycles to try to cover all possible interactions. But there is much scope for a broadening of outlook, technology transfers, and the development of joint projects with other groups that already have complementary expertise and facilities. In many cases similar problems are being faced, but in different environments; for example, the need to

obtain micro-meteorological data, and to quantify trace gas fluxes, at both the land and ocean surfaces.

2.4.3 Land use and water resources

The human capability to change the global climate is recent (IPCC 1996). However, global-scale, anthropogenic changes to land cover are several centuries old. Agriculture, mining, forestry and other land management practices have markedly altered at least 50% of the Earth's land surface; even tropical forests are rarely in a fully pristine state. From the human perspective, such land use changes have brought many benefits. But they can also have adverse environmental impacts, on biodiversity, land erosion and water quality. These problems are not new, but the rate and scale of current changes now demand more careful stewardship of the land.

In the UK, many land use changes have occurred over the past 50 years, despite relative population stability, and further significant changes can be expected. Previous inter-agency initiatives have addressed the ecology of farmland and changing farm economies: there is now need to extend that work, to assess a wider range of land use issues, such as the rehabilitation of contaminated or degraded land and the management of the coastal zone (Section 2.3.5). We should also address land use changes occurring in developing countries, frequently forced by global drivers and having global consequences. Issues of particular importance for systemic GER include:

- i) The theoretical links between the human causes of land use change and resulting changes in land cover. The dynamics of local and distant socio-economic forces need to be quantified, and related to the changes due to natural climate variability and climate change scenarios. Scaling issues are particularly important in this context.
- ii) Improved analysis of physical interactions between the atmosphere and the surface properties affected by land cover and land use (e.g. the fluxes of radiation, heat and water), primarily for the purposes of climate modelling (Section 2.3.3).
- iii) Improved analysis of the linkages between different land uses and biogeochemical cycles,

particular nutrient exchanges and source/sink fluxes for the main greenhouse gases (CO₂, CH₄ and N₂O; Section 2.3.4).

- iv) A better understanding of the sustainability of different land uses, particularly under conditions of climate stress. Degradation effects (e.g. erosion, desertification and salinization) are most acute in the tropics, but there are also serious consequences for temperate regions. For example, soil is currently being lost from farmland in Europe and the US at a rate that is estimated to be several times greater than the rate of its formation.
- v) Improved analysis of the linkages between different land uses, water management practices and the hydrological cycle, with particular regard to variability in freshwater quantity and quality (nutrients, biological properties and sediment loads) in rivers and reservoirs.

Several of the above issues emphasise the key role of soil properties (as already identified; Sections 2.2.3 and 2.3.3). Water availability and water use are also critical: moisture is as important as temperature in determining the structure and productivity of terrestrial ecosystems, and hence land uses and human development. Demand for water is growing more rapidly than population, and the World Bank estimates that over 80 countries have water shortages that threaten human health and economic viability. In most cases, the shortages are relative rather than absolute, reflecting an inadequate distributional infrastructure.

Although the UK is not on the World Bank list, a better appreciation of trends and natural variability is urgently needed for water management on the decadal scale, taking account of potential changes in the frequency of extreme events (droughts and floods). In addition to improved rainfall estimates on a local and regional basis, attention needs to be given to ground water quality; subsurface transport processes; the seasonal and interannual memory in the soil-vegetation system (affecting the catchment response to soil moisture and precipitation); and changes in agricultural demand, due to new crops and cropping patterns.

2.4.4 Ozone and UV-B

The 'ozone hole' issue shows that GER can itself influence the rate of global environmental change. Since the Montreal Protocol in 1987, there has been a significant worldwide reduction (by around 60% in Europe) in the emissions of CFCs and other ozone depleting substances, and the rapid rise in their concentrations in the lower atmosphere has been halted. However, these compounds have a very long life: it is therefore too early to expect the slowdown in CFC emissions to have restored ozone abundance in the upper atmosphere, where it acts as a screen for incoming UV-B radiation. Indeed, record low levels of stratospheric ozone were recorded in 1994-95, with seasonal depletions of around 95% at Halley Bay in the Antarctic (where the problem was first identified by UK researchers), around 50% at Arctic sites, and around 10% in mid-latitudes.

In the lower atmosphere, increased ozone is the main concern, brought about by elevated levels of nitrogen oxides and hydrocarbons. Whilst mostly associated with industrial activities in the northern hemisphere, elevated troposphere ozone levels also occur in the southern hemisphere, as a consequence of biomass burning.

Several GER issues relating to ozone and UV-B have already been identified (Sections 2.2.2, 2.3.1 and 2.3.2). Many of these problems also involve important links with climate (CFCs and ozone are both greenhouse gases, as are several CFC-substitutes), and with biogeochemical cycles (ozone interacts with nitrogen, carbon, sulphur and halogen compounds). As a result, a very wide range of human activities are directly and indirectly involved.

Examples of important research issues which bring together these aspects include:

- i) The incorporation of spatial effects in atmospheric chemistry models. For example, taking account of the patterning of ground-based sources of anthropogenic pollutants, affecting transport paths and vertical exchanges in the atmosphere. Related topics are the role of aircraft, with increasingly significant effects in the lower stratosphere, and of natural (volcanic) point source emissions of reactive chemicals.

ii) The socio-economic aspects of the CFC phase-out, including the factors affecting the implementation of the Montreal Protocol. Whilst alternative, non-CFC technologies have been developed, there is widespread non-compliance with reporting obligations and evidence of illicit trading - making it difficult to assess the need for further international measures to restrict the use of CFCs.

2.5 GER Growth Points

Complementing the underpinning and interactive research effort described above, support for the following GER growth points is strongly encouraged on the basis that their inter-agency stimulation would give highly cost-effective benefits (scientific and/or strategic) for the UK:

- the role of soil processes in global change, with emphasis on microbial diversity, trace gas exchanges, and biological and physical influences on hydrological properties
- adaptability of organisms and communities to environmental change, giving special attention to the tolerance of extremes of temperature, drought and other physical and chemical factors
- predictive modelling of the health impacts of global environmental change (climatic and non-climatic aspects), including comparative work that links human, veterinary and ecological perspectives
- the generic problem of using remotely-sensed observational data within models, to derive maximum benefit from new sources of satellite data that will soon become available
- the integrated analysis of resource management problems in the coastal zone, to involve both social and natural scientists
- biogeochemical modelling, to advance and test our understanding of large-scale ecosystem processes and their behaviour under conditions of global environmental change.

3. Enabling technologies and infrastructure

To address the research challenges identified here, UK researchers must have access to a wide range of observational data, covering the human, physico-chemical and biological components of the Earth system. For the natural science aspects, specialised facilities and research platforms are needed. These cover satellites, airborne sensors, mobile and in situ marine measurements, and land based experimental and monitoring facilities. Because of the high capital and operational cost of these items, the future support of many of them is uncertain. All data-gathering activities - and associated modelling work - are dependent on complementary laboratory facilities; in particular the provision of adequate computing services, data archives and data management support.

The UK is part of a European or worldwide effort for many GER observation activities. Significant benefits and reciprocal use of additional facilities are gained from such arrangements. We therefore need to maintain a strong scientific voice in the planning and development of work at the international level.

3.1 Data gathering platforms

3.1.1 Space borne sensors

Many unique and highly valuable observations can now be made from space, and quantitative techniques are being rapidly developed for their interpretation. Earth observation from satellites provides consistent global datasets which can be used to improve descriptions used in global models, to test and validate them, and to detect global changes. Such work is relevant to many processes in the Earth system, but considerable effort is required to organise the large volumes of data produced, and to use all the information effectively. UK scientists have a particularly good record in developing new methods for analysing such data, for the atmosphere, land and ocean surfaces, and for glaciology. However, many research problems remain, and advances in scientific understanding mean that there can and must be increasing emphasis on the use of the observations in analysis and modelling. Earth observation programmes must be closely linked to

scientific requirements, so as to make best use of observations, or directly to economic considerations, in order to justify the high costs involved.

Much of the UK expenditure on Earth observation is currently via subscriptions to European organisations, such as ESA or Eumetsat, or is committed to instrument development in bilateral agreements with space agencies such as ESA or NASA. ESA is currently developing plans for two types of mission: Earth Explorer satellites, of limited duration, to gain understanding for model development; and Earth Watch satellites, where long series of observations will be made with user co-funding (e.g. in collaboration with meteorological services). This twin-track approach by ESA is welcome, since it should ensure that new satellites are meeting high priority requirements, for either scientific or operational users. Thus, selection procedures for new satellites should in future include a scientific review, together with assessments of other user needs, and the economic benefits of the proposed mission.

There is strong international dependency in space-based observations, because the capital and launch costs mean that no nation can be self-sufficient in its Earth observation programme. Coordination is required to ensure that international duplication is minimised, and the scientific return on investment by individual countries is maximised. The UK should continue to take a leading role in such coordination activities.

3.1.2 Aircraft

Research aircraft are used to observe atmospheric phenomena and processes that need to be better represented in models. They can also be used for algorithm development, in conjunction with satellites, and as test beds for prototype instruments, aiding in their calibration and validation.

A recent EC study recommended a European network of 3-4 specialised aircraft for these purposes. The UK has one of these: the Meteorological Office C-130 aircraft, that is well-instrumented and has low-level flying ability. It has served as the UK passport into many

international programmes, providing access to information from platforms run by other countries, and it plays a vital role for GER, providing data on radiation, clouds, aerosols and tropospheric chemicals.

Recent efforts on the part of many agencies have recognised this value, but agencies must continue to work together to ensure the availability of an aircraft for long range and flexible operations and fitted with appropriate instrumentation.

3.1.3 Ocean measurements

As a maritime nation, the UK has a long and distinguished history in marine research: central to that strength is the availability of marine platforms. Three deep-sea research ships are currently available to the scientific community, all operated by NERC. These ships provide the only means to obtain chemical, biological and physical data over the full vertical depth range of the ocean; they are also essential for the calibration and validation of satellite data. GER studies requiring such platforms include: the role of the North Atlantic in climate change (including palaeo-aspects); the links between changes in marine ecosystems, mixing regimes, nutrients and pollutants; air-sea fluxes of greenhouse gases and aerosols; and the potential enhancement of the ocean carbon sink.

NERC is currently unable to fund fully the field deployment of its research fleet. Nevertheless, it is essential for GER that sufficient shiptime continues to be available to allow the necessary *in situ* measurements to be made. Much of this work is carried out in collaboration with international colleagues, providing access to additional data; furthermore, the UK has to date had strong influence on the overall design and planning of international oceanographic programmes.

On a 10-20 year timescale, the use of autonomous, long-range ocean sampling vehicles may reduce the need for research cruises and could eventually provide the basis for a sophisticated ocean observation system. There is a need to balance the high development costs and unproven feasibility of such devices against their potential large observational advantage. More modest investments in automated technology, with more certain scientific benefits, would involve improvements to data buoys, and the

equipping of commercial ships with sensor packages (e.g. for sea surface CO₂ measurements, using satellites for position logging and data transmission).

There is increasing dialogue between military and civilian marine authorities. The release of previously classified material would provide valuable additional observations for model development and other marine GER studies.

3.2 Land-based facilities and monitoring

The UK benefits from a wide variety of GER-related terrestrial observational and experimental facilities. These facilities support the collection of hydrological and meteorological data, and information on vegetation, land cover, and atmospheric surface variables and trace gas fluxes. In addition to providing basic research infrastructure, these support a range of longterm monitoring studies. It is essential that these capabilities are maintained and coordinated, and that they evolve as appropriate to meet the emerging scientific challenges discussed in section 2.

Examples of important ongoing activities and major facilities include:

- The Environmental Change Network, that has 17 sponsors and provides sites and support for physical, chemical and biological recording carried out according to standard protocols.
- The DoE-sponsored National Atmospheric Emissions Inventory. This is based at the National Environmental Technology Centre and covers the collection, collation and distribution of data on a range of trace gases and pollutants.
- Controlled environment facilities, at NERC and BBSRC Institutes and several universities, that allow the study of plant growth under environmental stress (such as CO₂, O₃, SO₂, NO_x and UV-B radiation).
- The world's largest, steerable meteorological radar at Chilbolton. This has both a direct and indirect observational role in GER, and is often used in conjunction with the C-130 aircraft. The

ownership and operation of this facility are now the responsibility of a number of agencies. Funding for its future use needs to be secured.

3.3 Global Observing Systems

Three worldwide data-gathering systems are currently being planned as a joint initiative by the main intergovernmental and non-governmental organisations with interests in global change: the Global Climate Observing System (GCOS), the Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS), and the Global Terrestrial Observing System (GTOS). Their purpose is to provide consistent, longterm datasets at fine scale spatial and temporal resolutions. These proposed systems are an integral part of the Climate Agenda, and will be discussed at an intergovernmental conference in 1997. The potential UK involvement is currently under review, through IACGEC, IACMST and the ECN Management Board.

Whilst the maintenance of current observing capabilities is likely to provide a satisfactory level of UK involvement, the gathering of equivalent data by developing countries will need additional effort. Funding bids for such work will need to be carefully assessed by national and multilateral aid agencies, in the context of their potential scientific and economic benefits.

3.4 Supercomputing and data management

3.4.1 Supercomputing facilities

The large range of spatial and temporal scales, and the complexity of the phenomena and processes involved, make powerful supercomputing essential for GER. The UK has, to date, been a world leader in developing climate prediction capabilities, using computer-based models to gain a preliminary understanding of the dynamic behaviour of the atmosphere and oceans.

However, the supercomputing power available to UK university groups (through the Research Councils) has not recently kept up with scientific requirements, falling below that available to researchers in the USA and Europe. A recent allocation of £10m for High Performance Computing will help to remedy this situation,

allowing progress to be resumed. Nevertheless, the demands of this field of research are such that regular investments of this magnitude will be necessary, approximately on a biennial basis.

Computing power by itself is not sufficient. Thus supercomputing capabilities need to be combined with very large data storage (see below) and interactive interpretation facilities to provide a fully useful research tool.

3.4.2 Data management activities and policies

A major constraint for many aspects of GER is the scarcity of global-scale data at appropriate spatial and temporal resolution. It is essential that data processing, curating and distribution activities receive longterm support, through the main Research Council data centres and facilities. This effort needs to be accompanied by better integration of data management into experimental and theoretical activities.

GER-related data should be recognised as a highly valuable national resource, underpinning a wide range of scientific, industrial and social needs. Opportunities for the pooling of data resources through national and international cooperation need to be developed further. It is essential that there is free access, preferably at no or marginal cost to the researcher, to data for non-commercial research, to ensure the optimum exploitation of data resources and their availability for modelling, prediction and impact assessment studies.

Fig.3 GER interests of research councils, government departments and other funding agencies in relation to the GER triad.
See Table 3 for acronyms

4. Communication and coordination

4.1 Public awareness, partnerships and education

Researchers involved in GER have responsibility for communicating the new knowledge and ideas that they obtain, bringing them to the attention of research users and assisting with relevant educational activities. Three aspects are of particular importance, in addition to the conventional methods for the discussion and publication of scientific results.

First, there is need to *develop wider awareness of the problems of global environmental change*. The measures necessary to avert or reduce the deleterious effects of global change may be politically unattractive: under such circumstances, they can only be introduced (and made to work effectively) if there is public consent and understanding. Yet it is not an easy task to communicate information on the complex scientific issues that are involved: many aspects of GER are abstract, technical or longterm, and it may be difficult to establish a direct link with people's everyday lives.

Furthermore, public perceptions of risk generally show a poor match with statistical probabilities, even when that information is explicitly provided. From a natural science perspective, such behaviour is irrational; however, the interpretation of the social scientist is that such risk assessments are frequently rational when understood in the context of other salient factors, including value judgements (e.g. with regard to the acceptability of different threats) and the level of trust in the ability of relevant institutions responsible for handling the risk in question, all of which are equally valid and real. Ethical and cultural considerations are therefore highly relevant in this context.

Difficulties in communicating information on GER to a wider audience can be exacerbated by an apparent lack of scientific consensus, with media attention attracted to unconventional views, or genuine disagreements between experts. There are several ways in which these problems can be addressed:

- Constructive dialogue within and between the scientific community and other sectoral groups to ensure the proper communication of scientific uncertainty and the relative confidence levels in predictions and assessments. This needs to be a two-way dialogue for mutual understanding and learning.

- The tangible, local implications of global environmental issues need to be stressed so as to engage public attention.

- GER researchers need to develop new partnerships with many sectoral groups of research users, not only those representing government and industry, but also professional bodies and institutes (e.g. for engineers, financial services, environmental consultants and aid agencies) and other non-governmental organisations with environmental interests.

- Issues about the legitimate interpretation of scientific information by pressure groups (whether 'green' or industrial) need to be addressed in a constructive way.

Second, the interdisciplinary nature of GER requires additional *training for policy-makers and researchers*, to develop competence at many levels. The broader, integrative outlook required for GER is not a substitute for in-depth expertise in a particular discipline: those involved must build on traditional skills to encompass extra areas of knowledge and learn the languages of other specialists. High quality training in GER, (from workshops to courses and research studentships), must therefore be an integral part of the study of global environmental change.

Finally, there are *international educational opportunities* made possible by UK GER strengths, and these are an exportable commodity. In addition to the direct cash benefits of a higher education sector with a world class reputation in this field, we have wider responsibilities to promote scientific development through overseas aid and the range of post-UNCED mechanisms on the basis of mutual self-interest in environmental security.

Table 3 - Research Council and Government Department/Executive Agency interests in GER (including in brackets estimated relevant expenditure - 1995/96 in £M)

	Research Councils
Biotechnology & Biological Sciences (BBSRC) (2.0)	<p>Plant acclimatisation to environmental stress.</p> <p>Nutrient dynamics: interactions with organic matter.</p> <p>Industrial products of crops/non-food products of crops.</p> <p>Development of clean technologies to reduce emissions of greenhouse gases; environmental biotechnology - microbiological degradation of in-situ persistent complex organic pollutants.</p> <p>Research strategy towards sustainable agriculture.</p> <p>Interactions between agricultural practice, biological systems and biodiversity.</p>
Economic & Social Research (ESRC) (2.9)	<p>Human drivers of environmental change (population dynamics; economic activity; individual and corporate perceptions, attitudes and behaviour). Socio-economic impacts of change: environmental risk assessment techniques and uncertainty.</p> <p>Technological change and the management of innovation; the use, diffusion and effectiveness of clean technologies to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and pollution.</p> <p>National and international policy formulation and implementation.</p> <p>Sustainable development including local responses/community initiatives.</p>
Engineering & Physical Sciences (EPSRC) (1.0)	<p>Development of clean technologies to reduce emissions of greenhouse gases and pollution - fuel cell technology; cleaner and more efficient combustion systems and synthesis; recycling, reuse and recovery in industry; coastal protection; sustainable cities; transport infrastructure.</p>
Medical (MRC) (0.8)	<p>Human population dynamics as a driver of environmental change; options for fertility control.</p> <p>Impacts of climate change, UVB and tropospheric pollution on human health.</p>
Natural Environment (NERC) (40.0)	<p>Processes within and between the atmosphere, ocean, sea ice, terrestrial systems, (including clouds, fluxes of energy, nutrients and gases). Earth radiation budget studies. Spatial and temporal variability.</p> <p>Observational and modelling studies to improve and quantify understanding of the primary sources, chemical interactions and transport of gases and particulates in the troposphere.</p> <p>Influence of polar regions on global systems and their response to environmental change.</p> <p>Integrated atmospheric, hydrological and biological modelling of impacts on land surfaces.</p> <p>Impacts of climate change, increased UVB radiation and atmospheric pollution on ecosystems.</p> <p>Factors controlling the origins, maintenance and loss of biological diversity and how changes affect ecosystem processes; factors influencing distribution and abundance of organisms and community assembly; role of habitat in maintaining diversity.</p>

Government Departments and Executive Agencies	
Agriculture, Fisheries & Food (MAFF) (15.0)	Fate of plant nutrients, nitrogen and phosphorus, gaseous emissions from agriculture. Impacts of climate change on agriculture. Flood warning and coastal protection. Changes in agricultural use - production of non-food products from crops.
British National Space Centre (BNSC) (53.0)	Earth Observation satellites: ERS1 & 2; ENVISAT and Polar Platform.
Conservation Bodies (EN/SNH/CCW)	Countryside Council for Wales, English Nature and Scottish Natural Heritage: Protection and sustainable use of Welsh, English and Scottish ecosystems respectively - impacts of climate change, land use change and pollution.
Environment (DoE) (29.0)	Monitoring, prediction, scale and causes of anthropogenic climate change and stratospheric ozone depletion. Impacts of climate change and ozone depletion. Better understanding of sources, especially of particles, of ozone on a European scale, and quantification of improvements to air quality, of the costs of control measures and of exposures of populations to air pollutants. Ensure adequate management of water supplies and protect UK freshwater and marine environment. To assist in conserving biodiversity and natural habitats globally. Policy lead Climate Change Convention, Montreal Protocol and Biodiversity Convention.
Environment Agency (EA) (operational 1996)	Protection and sustainable use of UK water resources and flood prevention/alleviation - impact of climate change. Modelling pathways of pollutants through the environment and estimating pollutant impacts, including critical loads assessment methods to power station emissions improvement plans.
Forestry (FC) (1.6)	Protection and sustainable exploitation of forestry resources
Health (DoH) (0.4)	Health impacts of climate change, increased UV-b radiation and atmospheric pollution
Meteorological Office (MetO) (3.4)	Development of coupled and unified models for monitoring, measuring and predicting climate change.
Overseas Development (ODA) (3.7)	Environmental sustainability in developing countries; research covering greenhouse gases, climate change, ozone, forestry, water and food.
Scottish Office (SO) (1.1)	Impacts on Scottish agriculture and fisheries.
Trade & Industry (DTI) (25.0)	Development of cleaner technologies for energy provision and greenhouse gas abatement -specifically initiatives for cleaner coal technologies and the development of renewable energy technologies.
Transport (DTp) (1.9)	Greenhouse gas emissions from the transport sector and climate change consequences of those emissions. Atmospheric pollution and transport sector.
Welsh Office (WO) (0.2)	Impacts of climate change and atmospheric pollution.

4.2 Coordination between funding agencies

Figure 3 and Table 3 show the large number of national funding bodies supporting work relevant to the GER agenda. Such activities illustrate the need for joint planning at several levels. Much coordination already takes place on a bilateral or trilateral basis, such as between NERC and DoE, MAFF and BBSRC, or EPSRC and DTI. Overall national coordination is provided by the Inter-Agency Committee on Global Environmental Change (IACGEC), responsible to the government's Office for Science and Technology (OST). The main funding agencies for UK GER are represented on IACGEC at the Chief Executive level, with secretariat support provided by the UK GER Office.

For most underpinning research issues (Section 2.2), these mechanisms provide an adequate basis for programme development and funding. However, for interactive and systemic research (Sections 2.3 and 2.4), addressing the major Earth system challenges, deficiencies can arise, and it would seem desirable for other coordination approaches to be explored, in collaboration with the scientific community.

Inter-agency collaboration on climate-related atmospheric research is one example of immediate importance. Thus the DoE funding of climate prediction at the Hadley Centre assumes that the underlying basic research is already being funded by NERC. The Meteorological Office receives core funding from the MoD to support work on understanding the natural climate variability and dynamics. There are both benefits and tensions arising from the expectations of the policy-driven research community and the research aims of the wider scientific community. There needs to be clarification and agreement between agencies over the complementary nature of their research agendas.

An important component of the UK strength in atmospheric science has been the basic research programme of the Meteorological Office. With the transition to trading fund status the research base must be protected. As this report makes clear, better understanding of atmospheric processes is essential for GER. The relevant agencies must determine mechanisms for the support of UK atmospheric science at the level

necessary to carry out an effective research programme before any attrition occurs.

4.2 Coordination between researchers

Individual scientists involved in GER have developed many working links with their national and international colleagues in closely aligned areas of interest, and the UK GER Office assists in relevant information exchange. However, there is no single national group or committee with responsibility to:

- Oversee GER coordination between research groups with different disciplinary backgrounds.
- Stimulate the development of new contacts and interactive research initiatives.
- Carry forward the policy review initiatives of the IACGEC on an inter-agency basis; for example, through multidisciplinary workshop meetings on interactive and integrative research topics.

The overall need is to ensure that maximum advantage is obtained from the national investment in GER. Under existing arrangements, there is a real risk that the synergistic benefits that may be derived from special programmes, and the potential value of many data-gathering exercises, will not be fully exploited by the scientific community, and hence will not become available to research users.

As already noted, a relatively long timescale is necessary for many GER studies. Current UK funding structures for GER are largely based on thematic programmes: these provide an effective way of developing a research community, but present particular problems in sustaining momentum once it has been developed. As a result, world-class expertise seems likely to be lost (with newly-trained researchers moving to other scientific fields) when the current generation of GER-related programmes come to an end.

Changes in existing coordination mechanisms are considered necessary to address these problems in a coherent way, by either altering or extending the role of the IACGEC in order to simplify linkages

between other already-established structures. Several national bodies include in their terms of reference the promotion of wider collaborations and forward planning for GER-related work; however, their combined efforts only cover part of the relevant national research effort, and the relationships between them are not well-defined (e.g. between those supported by the Research Councils and the Royal Society).

Whilst the Royal Society is not a major funding agency for GER, it has recognised responsibilities for national participation in non-governmental international research activities, particularly those under the aegis of the International Council of Scientific Unions (ICSU). Thus the Royal Society supports a Working Group on the International Geosphere-Biosphere Programme (that serves as the National IGBP Committee) and the UK Committee for the Global Energy and Water Cycle Experiment, GEWEX (a component of the

World Climate Research Programme). However, NERC committees provide the national links to other WCRP projects, and to some components of IGBP.

In the light of the recent decision of ICSU to co-sponsor a restructured International Human Dimensions of Global Environmental Change Programme (IHDP), it now seems appropriate for the IACGEC and the Royal Society to consider establishing a unified National Committee for GER, covering the research agendas of WCRP, IGBP and IHDP. It is envisaged that three main sub-groups would operate, with responsibility for the scientific development of the national contributions to these programmes. Their close alignment would make it very much easier to develop new disciplinary linkages or an overview approach, working closely with the UK GER Office.

5. Conclusions and recommendations

5.1 The need for a national GER programme

- i) Human actions are altering global-scale properties and processes in ways that have many unknown implications. Sustainable development requires better knowledge of Earth system behaviour, directed at understanding the dynamics of socio-economic activities and the natural environment. This knowledge is urgently needed to develop appropriate responses - avoidance, mitigation or adaptation - to future threats to human well-being.
- ii) GER is both multi- and interdisciplinary, involving the study of many anthropogenic and natural systems that operate over a wide range of spatial and temporal scales. The interplay between these systems is of critical importance. GER must therefore involve the social sciences (including economics, law and ethics) as well as the natural sciences.
- iii) The dynamic properties of interacting, global-scale systems precludes total predictability. Nevertheless, new observational, analytical and theoretical tools provide scope not only for major advances in scientific understanding, but also for improved risk assessments, scenario development and policy formulation. Much progress has already been made; for example, with regard to climate change (although this is only one aspect of global environmental change).
- iv) The UK has achieved scientific excellence in many aspects of GER. These strengths provide an information advantage in a changing world, underpinning many aspects of economic activity and policy development at the national, regional and global level. More than 20 generic priorities (from eight Panels) of the 1995 Technology Foresight exercise are closely relevant to GER.
- v) Much of the current GER effort has been directly stimulated by interest in global environmental change. However, there is other work that contributes to GER but has primarily been developed for other reasons.

These boundary problems make it difficult for funding agencies to estimate their individual support for GER on a consistent basis, giving rise to associated uncertainties in the national total for GER expenditure. Nevertheless, the current UK effort seems similar in scale to that of other developed countries of similar size.

- vi) European and international GER programmes can add considerable value to the UK research effort, through coordinated scientific planning, data-gathering and analyses. In addition to providing opportunities for scientific leadership, strong participation in such programmes enhances national credibility and influence when GER-related international agreements and conventions are prepared. The effective implementation of such agreements requires commitments by both developed and developing countries, with associated needs for building research capacity in the latter.

Recommendation 1:

The UK should build on its scientific strengths in GER by developing a national GER programme of a longterm nature, maintaining total support at least at the current level.

Recommendation 2:

Funding agencies should indicate how they define GER when providing expenditure estimates. Existing national and international data should be interpreted with caution.

Recommendation 3:

The UK GER effort should be developed in ways that derive maximum added value from international global change research programmes. The special environmental problems in developing countries should not be neglected.

Recommendation 4:

A fundamental objective of GER should be improvements in uncertainty assessment and management techniques that integrate technical, socio-economic, socio-political and ethical considerations in the context of the precautionary principle and risk assessment.

5.2 Research directions and priorities

- i) The pervasive and multidisciplinary nature of GER defies linear analysis or simple compartmentalisation. The conceptual approach proposed here comprises three perspectives (the human, physico-chemical and biological systems), with research at three levels (underpinning, interactive and systemic research) according to the strength of linkages between components. As GER matures and evolves, the need for new connections between different scientific fields becomes increasingly important. GER provides one of the most difficult and exciting scientific challenges for young scientists, the implications of which are addressed in section 5.4.
- ii) **Underpinning GER** provides the fundamental knowledge and technological capabilities, often (but not exclusively) on a single-discipline basis. Such work can mostly be considered GER-relevant, rather than GER-directed, since many other areas of human endeavour may also benefit. Key aspects, defined on the basis of national needs and expertise, are as follows:

■ From a *human system* perspective, priority topics for underpinning GER comprise: relations between industry and the environment; public perceptions, attitudes, ethics and behaviour; policy development processes; methods for assessing environmental damage and sustainably managing resource systems; the role and effects of international laws and institutions (including trade agreements); epidemiology and human fertility; technologies for emission abatement and waste minimisation; and the cost-effectiveness of energy efficiency measures.

■ From a *physico-chemical system* perspective, priority topics for underpinning GER comprise: natural variability of atmosphere, ocean and soil; atmosphere-ocean models; radiative behaviour of the atmosphere; chemistry of climatically important gases; land-ocean-atmosphere chemical exchange; stratospheric ozone and UV-B; improved regional predictions, particularly for extreme events; and data assimilation in models.

■ From a *biological system* perspective, priority topics for underpinning GER comprise: stress

tolerance of individual species; responses to environmental change that link ecology with physiology and molecular biology; the functional role of biodiversity; soil biological processes and their effects; transitional states of communities and ecosystems; and the natural variability of biological systems.

- ii) **Interactive GER** involves linkages between at least two of the three main scientific perspectives, investigating how one system affects another. Research on the following interactive issues is considered to be of priority importance for the UK: global change impacts on health; global change impacts on agriculture, forestry and fisheries; land surface properties and processes; the carbon and nitrogen cycles; changes in coastal systems; and past global changes. Specific GER topics of high scientific or strategic interest are identified in the text (Sections 2.3.1 - 2.3.6) for each of these issues.

- iii) **Systemic GER** provides the overall framework, building on interactive and underpinning research to address the 'grand challenges' of Earth system science. These are identified as: integrated climate studies; biogeochemical cycles; land use and water resources; and ozone and UV-B. All these main themes are highly important to UK economic interests. They also match international priority concerns, with many associated policy and legal developments.

- iv) **GER Growth Points** provide highly cost effective opportunities to build upon and complement the underpinning, interactive and systemic research described above. It should be stressed that such growth points are both additional to, and integral parts of, the research agenda and as such are contingent on continued support for other components in the GER triad. Growth points identified are: the role of soil processes in global change; adaptability of organisms to environmental change; predictive modelling of the health impacts of global environmental change; use of remotely-sensed observational data within models; integrated analysis of resource management problems in the coastal zone; biogeochemical modelling of large scale ecosystem processes.

Recommendation 5:

The UK GER portfolio for the next 5-10 years should be based on science of the highest quality that addresses the generic priorities identified in this Report. Although wide in coverage, there is already a close match between these subject areas and the GER-related topics identified in the current Forward Looks of the funding agencies.

Recommendation 6:

Within the total GER expenditure, there needs to be an appropriate balance between the wider support of GER-relevant work (through underpinning research) and integrated research initiatives, that directly address global environmental change problems (through interactive and systemic research).

Recommendation 7:

The funding agencies should direct their coordinating efforts towards the development of work which links the three main perspectives on GER, with particular attention given to any gaps or overlaps that might result from their individual activities.

5.3 Enabling technologies and infrastructure

- i) GER is highly dependent on large scale observational data. Research aircraft and ships are essential for *in situ* measurements to investigate atmospheric and ocean processes. The increasing availability of Earth observation data from satellites offers many exciting research opportunities. International coordination is essential to ensure that there is maximum scientific return from these technological developments.
- ii) The UK GER effort currently benefits from a wide range of land-based facilities for monitoring and experimental work, with relatively well-developed environmental capabilities in public sector laboratories and universities. However, future arrangements for their support are, in many cases, uncertain.
- iii) The maintenance of current national observational facilities would provide strong

UK coverage for the proposed Global Observing Systems (for Climate, Ocean and Terrestrial Systems). Proposals for wider UK effort will require careful consideration.

- iv) Progress in modelling (and predicting) global environmental change requires powerful supercomputers, together with facilities for high-volume data storage and interactive interpretation. Relatively large investments are needed to maintain such capabilities at the required level.
- v) Data charges for scientific research of a non-commercial nature should be set as low as possible, in order to make the widest and most effective national use of data resources, and to provide mutual benefits from international data-exchange arrangements.

Recommendation 8:

The relevant UK funding agencies should collaborate to ensure the future availability of adequate research aircraft and deep sea vessels.

Recommendation 9:

The UK should continue its strong involvement in all aspects of Earth observation programmes, with emphasis on interpretation of data and their use for model development.

Recommendation 10:

When considering options for re-structuring public sector laboratories, attention should be given to safeguarding the unique and essential role of many of them for UK GER, through longterm strategic research, monitoring and survey, and data management.

Recommendation 11:

Funding agencies' provision of supercomputing and data-handling facilities must continue to take account of the evolving needs of the UK GER programme.

5.4 Communication and coordination

- i) Those involved in GER need to establish constructive dialogue with the users and beneficiaries of their work, in government, industry, professional bodies and other non-governmental organisations. In an even wider context, attention must also be given to addressing the wider issues of public awareness and perception regarding global environmental change, with particular care taken to address uncertainty in a societal context.
- ii) GER provides one of the most exciting and difficult challenges for science and society. Education and training are therefore essential at all levels to ensure the future cadre of young scientists and also to ensure a proper basis for informed public debate on complex global issues. The UK has a strong tradition in overseas education and training which, allied to our scientific strengths in GER, provides a sound basis for a leading international role in knowledge and technology transfer.
- iii) The complex nature of the science and the inter-dependence of funding agencies' interests in GER presents particular requirements for coordination and collaboration. These needs are growing, as integrative links become increasingly important for the national GER programme, both within and between the natural and socio-economic sciences.
- iv) The current structure of the IACGEC is primarily directed at overall policy issues, rather than either scientific development or

the involvement of industry and commerce. Many international GER links are at present provided through the Royal Society, as the formal contact point for UK involvement in relevant ICSU programmes (World Climate Research Programme, WCRP; International Geosphere-Biosphere Programme, IGBP; and International Human Dimensions of Global Environmental Change Programme, IHDP). The Royal Society also covers the Commonwealth, giving it a unique international dimension.

- v) Whilst it may be necessary for separate groups to coordinate national participation in such activities, a unified forum that can integrate their overall scientific development, and promote interdisciplinary, integrative activities would seem advantageous, working closely with the UK GER Office.

Recommendation 12:

Effort should be given to increasing the effectiveness of communicating information, stimulating informed debate, developing partnerships with research users, and providing training on global environmental change at many levels, both in the UK and overseas.

Recommendation 13:

The feasibility of establishing a National Committee for GER should be explored by IACGEC, the Royal Society and other relevant bodies.

Annex 1 - Membership of IACGEC Expert Panel

Chairman

Professor Brian Hoskins University of Reading

Members

Professor Mike Begon University of Liverpool

Professor Robert Gurney University of Reading

Professor Peter Liss University of East Anglia

Professor Richard Macrory Imperial College of Science, Technology and Medicine

Professor Terry Mansfield University of Lancaster

Professor Tony McMichael London School of Tropical Medicine

Professor Jim Skea University of Sussex

Dr Camilla Toulmin International Institute for Environment & Development

Professor Kerry Turner University of East Anglia

Secretariat

Mr Steve Morgan UK Global Environmental Research Office

Dr Ian Simpson UK Global Environmental Research Office

Dr Phillip Williamson Natural Environment Research Council

Annex 2 - Relationship between research issues on GER triad (Figure 2) and Technology Foresight Priorities (Table 1) and Economic sectors (Table 2)

GER issue	Technology Foresight Panels								Economic sectors											
	A N R E	C h e m i c a l s	C o n s t r u c t i o n	E n e r g y	F o o d & D r i n k	I n f o T e c h	M a t e r i a l s	T r a n s p o r t	F o o d & A g r i c u l t u r e	E n e r g y & T r a n s p o r t	W a t e r	I n s u r a n c e	C i v i l E n g i n e e r i n g	C h e m i c a l s e t c	P o l l u t i o n c o n t r o l	R e m o t e S e n s i n g	D e f e n c e	H e a l t h	T o u r i s m	C o n s u l t a n c y
Underpinning																				
Socio-economic																				
Technological responses																				
Epidemiology & fertility																				
Species Interactions																				
Functional role of biodiversity																				
Soil processes																				
Ecosystem transition																				
Biological variability																				
Physico-chemical variability																				
Ocean/atmos models/fluxes																				
Radiative forcing																				
Atmospheric chemistry																				
Stratospheric ozone & UVB																				
Extreme events																				

	ANRE	Chemicals	Construction	Energy	Food & Drink	Info Tech	Materials	Transport	Food & Aggri	Energy & Transport	Water	Insurance	Civil Engineering	Chemicals etc	Pollution control	Remote Sensing	Defence	Health	Tourism	Consultancy
Interactive																				
Land surface processes																				
Past global change																				
Carbon and Nitrogen cycles																				
UVB & agriculture																				
Vector borne diseases																				
Biotechnology developments																				
Agriculture, Fish & Forestry																				
Human health																				
Changes in coastal systems																				
Atmospheric emissions																				
Systemic																				
Integrated climate studies																				
Biogeochemical cycles																				
Land use & water resources																				
Ozone & UVB																				

Footnotes

1. All areas of science identified in the GER triad also relate to one or more of the priorities identified by the Technology Foresight Programme Steering Committee.
2. ANRE = Agriculture, Natural Resources and Environment

Annex 3 - Submissions to the Expert Panel received from the scientific community

Professor J M Anderson, Institute of Arable Crops Research, Rothamsted International

Dr Martin Angel, Southampton Oceanography Centre

Professor Don Baulch, University of Leeds

Mr Max Beran, NERC Institute of Hydrology

Professor Keith Browning, University of Reading

Dr Eileen Buttle CBE, University of Oxford

Dr Bruce Callander, Meteorological Office

Professor Andrew Clarke, British Antarctic Survey

Mr Paul Ekins, Birkbeck College, University of London

Dr Paul Freund, IEA Greenhouse Gas R&D Programme

Dr John Gash, NERC Institute of Hydrology

Professor John Grace, University of Edinburgh

Professors Robin Grove-White and Brian Wynne, University of Lancaster

Professor J Gwynfryn Jones, Freshwater Biological Association

Professor Roy M Harrison, University of Birmingham

Professor O W Heal, University of Edinburgh

Dr R B Heywood, British Antarctic Survey

Professor Stephen Holgate, University of Southampton, Southampton General Hospital

Dr John Ingram, University of Oxford

Professor Paul G Jarvis, University of Edinburgh

Dr Geoff Jenkins, Hadley Centre, Meteorological Office

Professor Paul Mather, University of Nottingham

Dr Raymond Pollard, Southampton Oceanography Centre

Professor Noel Sheehy, Queen's University Belfast

Dr Graham Shimmield, University of Edinburgh

Dr Bernard Tinker, University of Oxford

Professor Andrew Watson, University of East Anglia

Dr Ann Webb, UMIST

Professor Brian Wilkinson, NERC Centre for Ecology and Hydrology

Annex 4 - International and regional research activities relevant to GER

World Climate Research Programme (WCRP)

Arctic Climate System Study (ACSYS)
Climate Variability and Predictability (CLIVAR)
Global Energy and Water Cycle Experiment (GEWEX)
Stratospheric Processes and their Role in Climate (SPARC)
Working Group on Numerical Experimentation (WGNE)
World Ocean Circulation Experiment (WOCE)

International Geosphere-Biosphere Programme (IGBP)

Biospheric Aspects of the Hydrological Cycle (BAHC)
Global Change and Terrestrial Ecosystems (GCTE)
International Global Atmospheric Chemistry Project (IGAC)
Joint Global Ocean Flux Study (JGOFS)
Land Ocean Interactions in the Coastal Zone (LOICZ)
Past Global Changes (PAGES)
Land Use/Cover Change (LUCC)
Data and Information System (DIS)
Global Analysis, Interpretation and Modelling (GAIM)

International Council of Scientific Unions (ICSU)

Scientific Committee on Problems of the Environment (SCOPE)
Scientific Committee on Oceanic Research (SCOR)
Scientific Committee on Antarctic Research (SCAR)

System for Analysis, Research and Training (START)

Ocean Drilling Programme

International Human Dimensions Programme (IHDP)

European Union Fourth Framework Programme

Environment and Climate Programme
Marine Science and Technology
Agriculture and Fisheries

United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) - Environment Assessment Programme

United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organisation (UNESCO)

Man and the Biosphere Programme (MAB)
International Hydrological Programme (IHP)
Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission

Food and Agriculture Organisation of the United Nations (FAO)

World Meteorological Organisation (WMO)

World Weather Watch Programme
World Climate Programme (umbrella programme for WCRP - see above)
Atmospheric Research and Environment Programme
Hydrology and Water Resources Programme

Annex 5 - Acronyms and abbreviations

BBSRC	Biotechnology and Biological Sciences Research Council
BNSC	British National Space Centre
CCW	Countryside Council for Wales
CFC	Chloroflourocarbon
DoE ¹	Department of the Environment
DoH	Department of Health
DTI	Department of Trade and Industry
DTp	Department of Transport
EA	Environment Agency
EC	European Commission
ECN	Environmental Change Network
EN	English Nature
EPSRC	Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council
ESA	European Space Agency
ESRC	Economic and Social Research Council
FC	Forestry Commission
FCCC	Framework Convention on Climate Change
GATT	General Agreement on Tariff and Trade
GCOS	Global Climate Observing System
GER	Global Environmental Research
GEWEX	Global Energy and Water Cycle Experiment
GOOS	Global Ocean Observing System
GTOS	Global Terrestrial Observing System
IACGEC	Inter-Agency Committee on Global Environmental Change
IACMST	Inter-Agency Committee on Marine Science and Technology
ICSU	International Council of Scientific Unions
IGBP	International Geosphere-Biosphere Programme
IGFA	International Group of Funding Agencies for Global Change Research
IHDP	International Human Dimensions of Global Environmental Change Programme
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
ISSC	International Social Science Council
MAFF	Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food
MetO	Meteorological Office
MRC	Medical Research Council
NASA	US National Aeronautics and Space Administration
NERC	Natural Environment Research Council
ODA	Overseas Development Administration
OECD	Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development
OST	Office of Science and Technology
SET	Science, Engineering and Technology
SNH	Scottish Natural Heritage
SO	Scottish Office
UNCED	United Nations Conference on Environment and Development
UV-B	Ultra violet radiation (of wavelength 280-315nm)
WCRP	World Climate Research Programme
WO	Welsh Office

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